

Enhancing Dynamic Capabilities through Organizational Leadership amid COVID-19 Disruption

A case study of a Social Innovation Housing Project in Sweden

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Abstract

This thesis examines dynamic capabilities and leadership in a Swedish social sustainability-oriented housing project during the unprecedented 2020-2021 COVID-19 business disruption. It employs a descriptive case study approach, investigating the organization's ability to innovate in the face of the pandemic. Sweden's related health regulations required adaptations through digital transformation, the adoption of social and physical distancing policies and program testing and measurement delays. Dynamic capabilities literature emphasizes the role of innovation amid disruption, offering a useful analytical framework for examining organizations' evolutionary fitness. Organizations whose core business incorporates societal needs to promote social sustainability are unusually challenged to deliver services and social programs during a pandemic that limits or extinguishes physical and social interactions. To meet this extraordinary disruption, social sustainability-oriented organizations such as the object of the study must rapidly innovate. Adapting an existing dynamic capabilities framework to analyze the housing organization, this study finds leadership to be crucial to identify, build, and deploy organizational dynamic capabilities for innovation to address such challenges. The study contributes to the existing literature by developing a framework that provides clear connections between leaders, external micro and macro environments, customer value creation and organizational dynamic capabilities. Leaders who can adapt and help their organizations evolve are demonstrated to be an essential capability when dealing with disruptions to social innovations.

Keywords: dynamic capabilities, social innovation, strategic shared leadership, innovation culture, pandemic, social sustainability

Post-Thesis Defense Clarifications

Regarding customer value and competitive advantage in the adapted framework, in this case study competitive advantage is focused on to a lesser degree than value creation as this study investigates social innovation where cooperation and collaboration are more important than competition. There was a greater amount of contact with Interviewee D due to her unique role as the thesis authors' contact at the case organization. The hybrid approach enabled the study to leave open the question of discoverable leadership style in the case organization and was an intentional decision on the part of the thesis authors.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction, aim and problem	1
1.1. Background	2
1.1.1. Bergenborg housing	2
1.1.2. Pandemic challenges	3
1.2. Research problem	3
1.3. Aim and Contribution	4
1.4. Previous research	5
1.4.1. Social Sustainability and Innovation	5
1.4.2. Dynamic Capabilities	6
1.4.3. Leadership and Dynamic Capabilities	7
1.5. Layout	9
2. Theoretical Background	10
2.1. Dynamic Capabilities	10
2.2. Shared Leadership and Strategic Shared Leadership	12
2.3. Consumer value creation	14
3. Methodology and methods	15
3.1. Methodology	15
3.2. The Case Study Approach	15
3.3. The Application of the Qualitative Method to a Case Study	15
3.4. Interviews	16
3.5. Participants	17
3.6. Research design	18
3.7. Data analysis	18
3.8. Reliability and validity	19
3.9. Limitations	20
4. Presentation of the object of study	21
5. Descriptive analysis	22
5.1. Politics, culture and innovation	22
5.1.1. Politics	22
5.1.2. Culture	22
5.1.3. Innovation	23
5.2. Communication and customer value	23

5.2.1. Communication strategies	23
5.2.2. Customer value	24
5.3. Leadership	25
5.4. Dynamic capabilities system clusters identifying, building and deploying	27
5.4.1. Identifying (Sensing)	27
5.4.2. Building (Seizing)	28
5.4.3. Deploying (Transforming)	29
5.5. COVID-19	30
5.6. Summary of analysis	31
5.6.1. Politics, culture, and innovation:	31
5.6.2. Communication and customer value:	31
5.6.3. Leadership:	31
5.6.4. Dynamic capabilities and system clusters:	32
5.6.5. COVID-19:	32
5.6.6. Frameworks:	33
6. Results and discussion	35
6.1. Research question 1:	35
6.2. Research question 2:	37
6.2.1. Skilled appropriate leaders	38
6.2.2. Culture of innovation	39
6.2.3. Reliable Communication	40
6.2.4. Flexible Leadership Structure	41
7. Conclusion	43
7.1. Future Recommendations	43
7.1.1. Implications and Future Recommendations for Academia	43
7.1.2. Implications and Future Recommendations for Practitioners	44
7.2. Summary	44
Reference list	I
Appendices	i
Appendix A: Interview guide for interviews with interviewee A and B (English version)	i
Appendix B: Interview guide for interviews with interviewee C, D, and G.	iii
Appendix C: Follow up questions for interviewee C	v
Appendix D: Interview guide for interview with Interviewees E and F (English version)	vi
Appendix E: Follow up questions for interviewees E and F	vii

Appendix F: Interview guide for interviews with interviewees H	viii
Appendix G: Interview guide for interviews with interviewees I	ix
Appendix H: Informational letter sent to all interviewees (In Swedish, English version provided if requested)	x

Table of Tables

Table 1: Overview of all interviewees, how they participated in the study and their position as a stakeholder in relation to TLP.....	17–18
Table 2: Comparison of O’Connor (2008) elements for innovation with TLP’s unique dynamic capabilities.....	37

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Key ideas of building the right sources of a firm’s success (Breznik & Hisrich, 2014 p. 4).....	10
Figure 2: Systems-level view of dynamic capabilities and campus innovation activities (Heaton et al., 2020).....	33
Figure 3: Adapted Dynamic Capabilities Framework- System-level view of TLP.....	34
Figure 4: TLP leadership enhanced dynamic capabilities interactions in response to COVID-19 challenges.....	45

Terms and abbreviations

Social sustainability: Sustainable solutions for social problems oriented through the application of the UN SDG classification system.

SDGs: a collection of 17 interlinked global goals designed to be a blueprint for a better and more sustainable future set forth by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015.

Social sustainability-oriented business: firms or organizations whose core business plans include or are primarily oriented to improve social conditions of any kind.

Social innovation project: activities in the form of a defined project undertaken by an organization that aims to improve social conditions of any kind.

Social innovation: new ideas in the form of products, services or models that improve social conditions, meet social needs, create social relationships, and form new collaborations.

Global lockdown: “the shared experience of billions of people” (Collins dictionary, 1994) limiting normal human activity regarding the COVID-19 pandemic beginning approximately in November, 2019 in which all segments of societies were affected by the biggest pandemic in a century.

High touch: referring to high frequency, in-person interactions, especially within social service-oriented businesses

Dynamic capabilities: the ability to integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external competences to address rapidly changing environments, organized into clusters of activity.

Resource Based View (RBV): argues that firms possess resources, a subset of which enables them to achieve competitive advantage. A subset of those, in turn, leads to superior long-term performance. Resources that are valuable and rare can lead to the creation of competitive advantage.

Consumer value: the satisfaction the consumer experiences, or expects to experience, by taking a given action relative to the cost of that action.

Market orientation: an approach to business that prioritizes identifying the needs and desires of consumers and creating products and services that satisfy them.

Knowledge management: an organization’s capture, use, and analysis of the impact of a group's collective knowledge.

Customer relationship management (CRM): with a goal of improving business relationships for growth, it is a company's relationships and interactions with customers and potential customers.

Strategic Leadership: a leadership style highly applicable to top managers and boards whose decisions often set the direction for decision making throughout the organization.

Strategic Shared Leadership (SSL): firm leadership involving the purposeful sharing of strategic decisions. The process of making decisions between the dominant coalition that is initiated and implemented by a focal strategic leader or a small group of strategic leaders such as the CEO and Chair of the Board.

Shared Leadership: Shared leadership occurs when a group of individuals lead each other to achieve successful outcomes.

Organizational dynamic capabilities (ODCs): an organization's ability to integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external competences to address rapidly changing environments, organized into clusters of activity.

1. Introduction, aim and problem

It is critical for social sustainability-oriented businesses to identify and deploy their innovation capabilities in the face of novel exogenous disruptions such as the global COVID-19 pandemic. According to Vézina, Ben Selma, and Malo (2019), social innovation offers solutions to social problems previously or currently unsolved or poorly addressed by extant organizational or institutional frameworks. The European Commission (2021) defines social innovations as “new ideas that meet social needs, create social relationships and form new collaborations. These innovations can be products, services or models addressing unmet needs more effectively.” Both The World Economic Forum Global Risks Report (2020) and Gopinath (2020) state that due to the global lockdown, defined by Collins dictionary (1994) as “the shared experience of billions of people”, the global economy faced the worst recession since the great depression. Consequently, the 2020 pandemic has generated extraordinary interest in innovation at the global, national, and organizational level to meet the challenges (Manthiou, 2020). The scale and pace of business innovation in the context of the pandemic is unmatched in the last century and falls outside of ordinary exogenous business disruptions (Heinonen & Strandvik, 2020). Innovation in response to disruption can make the difference between business failure and success. Such disruption highlights and magnifies how businesses must recognize, restructure, integrate, and generate innovative capabilities to survive and compete (Zhang, Amankwah-Amoah, & Beaverstock, 2019).

Innovation, therefore, is crucial during such an unusually acute disruption (Heinonen & Strandvik, 2020). The pandemic’s unprecedented societal and economic effects have been particularly challenging for social innovation-oriented businesses, as they must further adjust to meet their customers’ needs (Finsterwalder & Kuppelwieser, 2020). Core elements of such business activities may be difficult or impossible to deliver due to overriding public health exigencies and associated strategy and communication challenges, health and safety concerns and extreme uncertainty (Cortez & Johnston, 2020). “High touch” social service-oriented businesses that rely on frequent in-person interactions underwent drastic disruption to their core activities (Ferguson, Smith, & Kietzmann, 2021). Social sustainability-oriented housing projects with a substantial focus on shared common spaces to promote collaboration and social integration are unusually challenged due to their reliance on frequent in-person social interaction, or high touch (Arroyo, Montesino, Johansson, & Yahia, 2021). Such projects are challenged to innovate across social connection, physical distancing, communication, remote presence, and facility categories (Heinonen & Strandvik, 2020).

The antecedents to innovation are *dynamic capabilities*, defined as “the ability to integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external competences to address rapidly changing environments” (Teece, Pisano, & Shuen, 1997, p. 516). These capabilities are unique to each organization and feature dynamic flexibility; the abilities to change, configure, and improve these capabilities. The capabilities are strategically oriented and rely on a key and essential leader to identify and set them in motion (Breznik & Hisrich, 2014). Skilled leadership is essential during crises to guide organizations through disruption, and to identify, build, and deploy new and existing capabilities for successful responses to externally derived challenges (Dirani et al., 2020; Landroquez, Castro, & Cepeda-Carrión, 2011). Organizational leaders who successfully identify their dynamic capabilities, and particularly those leaders who sense opportunity and subsequently persuade others to act with haste, can withstand even serious business disruption (Baden-Fuller & Teece, 2019).

Leaders who can guide their organizations through the process of identifying, building, and deploying resources and capabilities, nurture innovation (Zott, 2003).

1.1. Background

This section presents its relevant history of the object of the case study and the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on its operations. It describes the organization's focus on social sustainability, and its innovations to solve local social challenges. Details of the Swedish government's restrictions in response to the COVID-19 pandemic that apply to the case study are also highlighted.

1.1.1. Bergenborg housing

In Bergenborg, Sweden, housing has traditionally featured siloed living options based on age, immigration status, and stage of life; students, pensioners, and recent refugees have tended to live apart from one another (Leiler, Bjärtå, Ekdahl, & Wasteson, 2019; Holmkvist & Turner, 2014). Bergenborg's citizens and politicians decided that this approach to housing did not sufficiently address, and indeed contributed to, the social challenges of loneliness and refugee social integration (Bergenborgshem website). According to a board member interviewee, municipal politicians responded to consistent input from the community to address loneliness, a growing mental health challenge identified in Sweden among the aging population and among newly independent 18 to 25-year-olds. Additionally, the community signaled a strong local interest in addressing the challenge of social, economic, and cultural integration of the recent population of refugee immigrants to Sweden from war-torn regions (*interview CEO, Board, April 9, 2021*).

Uniquely, leadership at the Bergenborgshem municipal housing organization, a for-profit publicly funded housing company, viewed the community's concern in these areas as an opportunity for innovation in the public housing industry. Based upon innovative intergenerational housing successes in Italy, Bergenborgshem leaders launched a two-year social innovation project, The Loneliness Project or "TLP," in one of their existing residential buildings to test the concept (Bergenborgshem website). According to an interviewee, such a decision is unusual in a Nordic real estate business where intergenerational, intercultural interactions and mental health improvement have not been a focus, even though municipal housing is a public service. No official municipal mandate existed to solve loneliness, aid refugee assimilation, or improve intergenerational relations, yet these social challenges affect Bergenborg and were undertaken through Bergenborgshem's TLP project (*interview CEO, Board, April 9, 2021*). Bergenborgshem's decision to address social problems with an innovative project is in keeping with European Commission (2021) recommendations for developing sustainable cities through innovations aimed at solving social problems.

In December 2019, Bergenborgshem launched TLP (Bergenborgshem website). The novel social innovation project addressed social problems brought on by isolated living patterns and specifically structured to promote high levels of social interaction through shared kitchen, dining, gaming, hobby, and meeting spaces. Because the project's strategy to address loneliness and integration was centered on spending time in community "togetherness spaces" to promote interaction, it was particularly vulnerable to the unexpected public health challenge of the global COVID -19 pandemic (Arroyo et al., 2021). The pandemic disrupted the project's core strategy and activities just ninety days after residents moved into the building. All the project stakeholders were faced

with significant challenges, disappointments, and disruption of their original visions for what living in the intergenerational, intercultural residence would be (*interview CEO, Board, April 9, 2021*).

1.1.2. Pandemic challenges

The constraints of COVID-19 social and physical distancing policies in Sweden represented an unusual challenge to the successful realization of high touch social innovation projects such as intergenerational multicultural residential housing. In December 2019, Sweden enforced a set of health guidelines to minimize the spread of the COVID-19 virus. These guidelines addressed individuals, communities and businesses stating that “All organizations in Sweden must ensure that they implement suitable measures to avoid the spread of COVID-19. It is particularly important to take into account vulnerable persons.” (Public Health Agency Folkhälsomyndigheten, n.d.) The Bergenborgshem TLP housing project was required to implement safe social and physical distancing measures in particular with respect to their elderly population which comprised approximately one third of the total residents (*interview CEO, Board, April 9, 2021*).

The COVID-19 pandemic offers a unique opportunity to study a social sustainability- oriented housing project’s capacity to innovate successfully not just under duress, but under conditions hampering social engagement in particular. Bergenborgshem, through its TLP residential living project, was expected to provide a novel living experience for residents according to the housing contracts they signed. Participants were carefully chosen after completing thorough interviews for their participation in a project possibly not suitable for all applicants (*interview CEO, Board, April 9, 2021*).

For their part, Bergenborgshem was to provide a specially designed residential atmosphere after having remodeled the physical space for the project social goals to address loneliness and refugee integration (Arroyo et al., 2021). This reconfiguration represented an investment in the facility itself. Moreover, these goals were in addition to providing housing according to the standards of Bergenborgshem’s regular business operations such as being on time and within budget and meeting several other sustainability requirements (Bergenborgshem Sustainability Report, 2020). The TLP project team was therefore responsible to lead, develop, and manage the housing project according to the requirements and criteria set forth by the board of directors and as expected by the project residents. This research seeks to explore the organization's actions and innovations through the dynamic capabilities, shared leadership, and strategic shared leadership theory lenses to better understand their response to these challenges.

1.2. Research problem

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted many businesses, requiring them to rapidly adapt and innovate to satisfy customers, especially businesses whose core activities and strategies rely on in-person interactions (Van Jaarsveld, 2020). According to Nguyen, Hargittai, and Marler (2021) and Xie, Charness, Fingerman, Kaye, Kim and Khurshid (2020), COVID-19 business disruption has been met with swift innovation in the form of physical space and program transformation, rapid digitalization, and changes to internal and external communication methods. Observed difficulties in program and project implementation have been due to mandated public health restrictions requiring limited or no contact between people, especially those over the age of 70 (Public Health Agency Folkhälsomyndigheten, n.d.). According to Teece (2007) and Eisenhardt and Martin (2000), disruption to a business’ core activity requires the deployment of its innovation capability.

Businesses whose activities, products, and services are innovative and focus on solving social problems, and thus fit the definition of social innovation, as described in the Introduction, are particularly challenged to deliver on their value proposition during a pandemic requiring physical and social distancing. Organizations that successfully identify their dynamic capabilities, especially those of noticing and responding to changing conditions by "...sensing... opportunities and persuading others that such opportunities are worth pursuing speedily with the resources at hand" (Baden-Fuller & Teece, 2019, p. 2), can weather serious business disruption. Dynamic capabilities theory conceptualizes that these capabilities are heterogeneous across businesses due to the unique nature of their positions and processes, and are built, not purchased, in relationship to their specific ecosystems (Teece, 2007). Moreover, Heaton, Lewin, & Teece (2020, p. 11) assert that "leaders are crucial to the development of such transformational dynamic capabilities". Unfortunately, very little attention has been given in literature to the exact nature of optimal leadership for identifying, building, and deploying dynamic capabilities to respond to serious or extreme business disruption and how to foster that leadership. This thesis project seeks to fill this gap.

1.3. Aim and Contribution

The aim of this thesis is to explore the leadership and dynamic capabilities of a social innovation housing company amid COVID-19 pandemic challenges. Bergenborgshem's The Loneliness Project (TLP) housing project is the case studied. The thesis investigates the organization's capabilities through two perspectives: (1) examining the processes through which the organization identifies, builds, and deploys capabilities; (2) the leadership practices, competencies, and styles employed by leaders relative to the capabilities. The advantage of focusing on capabilities and leadership amid COVID-19 pandemic is that it provides a more comprehensive understanding of the organization's evolutionary fitness. The dynamic capabilities framework allows for an interpretation of the role that unique dynamic capabilities may have in shaping the outcome of the housing project.

The research questions are therefore as follows:

RQ1: What are the case housing company's dynamic capabilities in the context of COVID-19 global pandemic challenges?

RQ2: How are dynamic capabilities identified, built, and deployed by leadership in a social sustainability-oriented residential housing project in the context of COVID-19?

The above-mentioned research questions are relevant in the context of social innovation for positive regional impact, in line with the European Commission's (2021) recommendations and the identified United Nations SDGs (United Nations, n.d. a; United nations n.d. b). This thesis contributes to the discourses on leadership for social innovation, as well as dynamic capabilities and innovation. Furthermore, the study tests a novel suggested framework for investigating leadership within dynamic capabilities based on an existing model (see Figure 2) (Heaton et al., 2020). This adapted framework (see Figure 3) contributes to both practitioners and academic discourses through clearly linking leaders, actions, and dynamic capabilities to value creation.

Finally, the thesis contributes an outline for future research with recommendations for both practitioners and academics.

1.4. Previous research

This chapter presents the academic discourse relevant to this thesis organized into three topics. First, social sustainability and social innovation are discussed providing the background for the object of the case study and to position the case in the broader field of social sustainability. In the foreground are the second and third research areas of dynamic capabilities and leadership which are summarized in this chapter and more specifically described as the theoretical framework this study employs.

1.4.1. Social Sustainability and Innovation

Sustainable solutions for social problems can be oriented through the application of the UN SDG classification system, as defined in the Terms and Abbreviations. For this study SDG's 10 and 11 are most relevant. Goal 10 'Reduce Inequalities' focuses on reducing inequalities within and amongst countries. Within this goal, the Bergenborgshem TLP project responds to the target 10.2 which states "By 2030, empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status" (United Nations, n.d. a). Goal 11 'Sustainable Cities and Communities' focuses on making human cities and settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable. Within this goal, the TLP project tackles target 11.1 which reads "By 2030, ensure access for all to adequate, safe and affordable housing and basic services and upgrade slums" (United Nations, n.d. b).

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Innovation Strategy (OECD, 2021) and EU Innovation policies (European Commission, 2021) both advocate for social innovation to solve sustainability challenges. The OECD (2021) claims that while no policy holds the answer to the economic, environmental, and social recovery needed in a post-crisis world, innovation is the key to any effort to improve society's quality of life. Innovation is also deemed essential in addressing some of society's most pressing issues. The OECD (2021) states that policies regarding innovation must be adapted to the new and ever-changing environments surrounding innovation and equip the wide variety of actors to undertake innovative actions. These actions should thus also benefit the actors. Therefore, the OECD (2021) highlights the following: the need to empower people and organizations to innovate, the importance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SME), the need for fundamental research and development (R&D), and science being a vital aspect of innovation.

The European Commission (2021) defines social innovations as "new ideas that meet social needs, create social relationships and form new collaborations. These innovations can be products, services or models addressing unmet needs more effectively." The main objectives identified by the European Commission (2021) are to promote social innovation as a source of growth and jobs, to share information about social innovation in Europe, and to support innovative entrepreneurs and to mobilize investors and public organizations. These objectives were set in order to meet the European Commission's (2021) greater objective of encouraging market uptake of innovative solutions and to stimulate employment. Additionally, according to Vézina et al. (2019), social innovation offers solutions to social problems previously or currently unsolved or poorly addressed by the organizational or institutional frameworks that are present.

Furthermore, Nicholls and Murdoch (2016) identified three levels of social innovation. The first level features incremental innovations within goods and services that are aimed at addressing one or more social needs. The second level is institutional innovation, also known as institutional change. This level focuses on reframing social and economic structures in order to create new social values and outcomes, for example the equitable trade relations promoted by the fair-trade movement. The final level is disruptive social innovation, the purpose of which is to create systems changes. This is often achieved through social movements and politicians, as well as through groups or networks that drive innovation with a vision of creating a change. An example of this is seen in power relationships and in reframing the social hierarchy to benefit marginalized groups (Nicholls & Murdoch, 2016; Vézina et al., 2019).

Social innovation-oriented businesses include solving society-based problems in their core business strategies. It differs from business innovation, which is rooted solely in commerce and competition. For the purposes of this research project, Dawson and Daniel's (2010) definition of social innovation organizations is the most precise for the case organization analysis. Dawson and Daniel (2010, p. 11) state that firms conducting social innovation programs and projects "implement new ideas that succeed in resolving social challenges, problems or opportunities by meeting social goals and improving societal well-being". Furthermore, Dawson and Daniel (2010) combine business and social innovation, conceptualizing "an event" which can be understood as a firm's project, program, or other novel undertaking. The components of the firm's social innovation project, for the purposes of this study, consist of the people, the challenge, the process, and the well-being goals.

1.4.2. Dynamic Capabilities

The ambitious aim of dynamic capabilities research centers on understanding how organizations can maintain a competitive advantage by responding to and creating environmental change (Teece, 2007; Helfat & Peteraf, 2009). Dynamic capabilities stretch across, and are directly involved in, the domains of strategy and content and involve multiple levels of analysis. This ranges from managerial decision-making processes to organizational routines, to competitive interactions and environmental change (Helfat & Peteraf, 2009). Therefore, much of the work remains conceptual and is focused on foundational level issues (Helfat & Peteraf, 2009). Dynamic capabilities theory is rooted in the resource-based view (RBV), as it is concerned with the organization's capabilities that have the potential to provide a competitive advantage (Helfat & Peteraf, 2009).

There are three definitions of dynamic capabilities that have been the most influential throughout the theory's development (Di Stefano, Peteraf, & Verona, 2009). First, Helfat and Peteraf (2009, p. 94), defined dynamic capabilities as "the capacity of an organization to purposefully create, extend, and modify its resource base". Teece, Pisano, and Shuen (1997) state that dynamic capabilities are comprised of organizational skills, resources, and functional competencies while Eisenhardt and Martin (2000) argue that dynamic capabilities alter an organization's resource base, which includes the organization's physical, human, and organizational assets. Additionally, Zollo and Winter (2002) claim that dynamic capabilities work with operational capabilities. Because there are many types of dynamic capabilities that result in different effects, the definition of the theory has been described in a more general form (Helfat & Peteraf, 2009). Therefore, it is

important for researchers to be specific in characterizing the particular dynamic capabilities that they are Investigating. Hence for the purpose of this research, the study adheres to Teece, et al. (1997) definition emphasizing an organization's skills, resources and functional competencies.

The usefulness of dynamic capabilities as a tool for managers and organizational leaders is revealed by Wang and Ahmed (2007) in their research aimed at constructing measurement tools and an integrated framework for leadership application within organizations. Leaders can benefit from adopting a dynamic capabilities approach to their organizations, according to Wang and Ahmed (2007), with the caveat that evaluation of organizational dynamic capabilities must not be a "stand alone target" (p. 44). Rather, multiple external factors, internal strategic orientation, and current and predicted strengths together can comprise a leadership path forward. A dynamic capabilities-oriented leadership model does not currently exist according to the literature conducted for this research thesis. However, prescriptions for leaders who employ dynamic capabilities as a means for understanding and leveraging organizational core competencies can be found in discourse focused on describing and exploring the potential of dynamic capabilities as a leadership tool.

1.4.3. Leadership and Dynamic Capabilities

In recent years leadership has been one of the most broadly studied topics. Leadership has been defined as "the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish shared objectives" (Pitelis & Wagner, p. 235, 2019). However, the dynamic capabilities literature does not feature extensive analysis and description of the role of leadership in organizational innovation. Nevertheless, in an analysis of university innovation, Heaton et al. (2020) reveals the importance of leadership and management through a description of three critical leadership components. First, leadership and management are deemed essential for value creation and delivery. Second, managerial and leadership emotional intelligence is found to be essential to successful leadership through a combination of coaching, democratic, affiliative, and authoritative leadership styles. Third, leadership skills such as coping with change, setting direction, and aligning people with the opportunity, empowering, motivating, and connecting people through networks are found to be essential to develop and sustain dynamic capabilities (Heaton et al., 2020). Management skills such as organizing, coping with complexity, planning, problem-solving, exercising control, and budgeting are also found to be crucial in the dynamic capabilities framework.

According to Heaton et al. (2020, p.6) leadership and management are defined as dynamic capabilities that together comprise an organization's "higher order need". Here, higher order refers to strategic leadership which is critical for the innovation related tasks described above, namely identifying, creating, and capturing opportunity. In the Heaton et al. (2020) model of dynamic capabilities for organizational innovation, leadership is both a dynamic capability and the driver of deployment of other dynamic capabilities necessary for successful organizational innovation. Hence, any analysis of an organization employing the dynamic capabilities framework must consider leadership and management. Without effective leadership and management, the "bold moves" necessary for an organization to achieve "evolutionary fitness", defined as the ability to sustain or increase competitive advantage, would not be captured, developed, and deployed (Heaton et al., 2020, p. 7).

Teece's (Heaton et al., 2020) dynamic capabilities system level framework includes organizations' interactions with local, regional, national and industry ecosystems (see Figure 2). The process of sensing, seizing, and transforming for value creation and capture is deemed as dependent upon leadership. Leaders are a dynamic capability themselves, but they are also the agents of action, setting the system components into motion. Dynamic capabilities are therefore found in organizational governance structures and processes. Hence to fully comprehend how organizations identify, prioritize and act on an opportunity for innovation, an analysis of leadership and management is necessary.

Furthermore, the dynamic capabilities framework identifies organizational activities involved with the three core theory components: sensing, seizing, and transforming as a way of understanding organizational innovation. The framework also identifies the importance of the ecosystems in which organizations operate. Against the backdrop of local, regional, industry, and other relevant ecosystems, leaders are revealed to be essential to the creation and capture of value from entrepreneurial activities. Furthermore, authors Heaton et al. (2020) find that strong dynamic capabilities, guided by the leaders in an organization, govern the evolutionary fitness of an organization. Therefore, according to this model, any analysis and discussion of organizations that undertake innovative projects contributing to organizational evolutionary fitness must investigate leaders and managers as dynamic capabilities themselves and as the agents of dynamic capability deployment.

Innovation leadership and management is also a key component of the entrepreneurship discourse. The innovation leader, sometimes synonymous with entrepreneurial leaders, is crucial to support growth development and adaptation in an organization that takes on a social innovation project (Heaton et al., 2020). Moreover, Heaton et al. (2020, p. 6) assert that "Entrepreneurial management constitutes the core of what we refer to as dynamic capabilities." Leaders are therefore considered to be a dynamic capability, as they act as the higher order force necessary to orchestrate other dynamic capabilities present in the system in which an organization operates. Leaders and their managers are advised to analyze the external environment to identify forces of change, develop and promote the strategic vision, identifying and deploying resources to meet the needs and opportunities at hand (Heaton et al., 2020). Dynamic capabilities and entrepreneurship discourses intersect when it comes to analyzing and exploring how organizations create and capture value either to sustain or create competitive advantage. Dynamic capabilities "involve higher level processes that can enable an enterprise... to direct its resources and activities toward high-payoff endeavors" (Heaton et al., 2020, p. 6). Due to the limitations of this study, the thesis will neither focus further on entrepreneurship discourse nor will it be featured in a later discussion.

Lastly, according to Schoemaker, Heaton, and Teece (2018), leaders who are able to operationalize and manipulate dynamic capabilities in a specific organizational setting are required. There are six leadership abilities, identified by Schoemaker et al. (2018), that are crucial in this regard. These leadership abilities are (1) Anticipate; (2) Challenge; (3) Interpret; (4) Decide; (5) Align; and (6) Learn. These leadership disciplines are closely linked to dynamic capabilities. In particular, the Anticipate, Challenge and Interpret skills build on the dynamic capability of sensing change. Additionally, the disciplines of Decide, Align, and Learn are tied to the dynamic capability of seizing opportunities. These six disciplines all feature in how to transform an organization (Schoemaker, Heaton, & Teece, 2018).

1.5. Layout

The remainder of the thesis is structured into the following chapters:

- Chapter 2: Theoretical Background. In this chapter the theoretical background where central concepts that ground this research are introduced to the reader. These are Dynamic Capabilities for Innovation, Shared Leadership and Strategic Shared Leadership, as well as Consumer Value Creation.
- Chapter 3: Methodology and Methods. In this chapter both the methodology and methods used in this study are introduced to the reader. This chapter is divided into the sections Methodology, The Case Study Approach, The Application of the Qualitative Method to a Case Study, Interviews, Participants, Research Design, Data Analysis, Reliability and Validity, and Limitations.
- Chapter 4: Presentation of the object of the study. In this chapter the object of the study is presented to facilitate reading and understanding of the text. Here, facts such as organizational structure and purpose are presented regarding the object of the study.
- Chapter 5: Descriptive Analysis. The Descriptive Analysis chapter is first divided into five sections based on themes identified within the interviews conducted. These themes are (1) Politics, Culture, and Innovation, (2) Communication and Customer Value, (3) Leadership, (4) Dynamic Capabilities System Clusters: Identifying, Building, and Deploying, (5) COVID-19. A Summary of Analysis is then presented where the key findings from the previous sections are outlined. This section concludes with a description of the Framework that was adapted for the purpose of this thesis.
- Chapter 6: Results and Discussion. This chapter is divided into two sections, each addressing one of the research questions. Within these sections, the unique findings of this study are discussed in relation to the literature previously presented in order to answer the research questions.
- Chapter 7: Conclusion. In this chapter final conclusions regarding this study's unique findings are outlined and future recommendations for practice and future research are discussed.

2. Theoretical Background

In this chapter, the theories and concepts most relevant to this thesis are introduced. These theories and concepts will then be used as a framework for the analysis and to answer the research questions. The following concepts and theories are discussed in this chapter: (1) Dynamic Capabilities for Innovation, (2) Shared Leadership and Strategic Shared Leadership, and (3) Consumer Value Creation.

2.1. Dynamic Capabilities

In their 1997 article, Teece et al. introduced the concept of dynamic capabilities as an organization's basic competencies which should be used to generate short-term competitive positions that can be developed into longer-term competitive advantage. Those authors note that dynamic capabilities theory conceptualizes leadership strategy development to adapt to radical discontinuous change, while maintaining capability standards to ensure competitive survival. The theory provides a more complex, rich framework based on the resource-based view (RBV) of the organization, which, as its name suggests, focuses on the organization's resources. Yet the resource-based view does not take into consideration the organization's ability to act and respond to its changing environment. Teece et al. (1997) derived their argument from observing organizations that once were thriving, struggling, or failing as their ecosystems changed around them (Harreld, O'Reilly III, & Tushman, 2007). Teece et al.'s (1997) model focused on the mechanisms through which organizations learn and accumulate new capabilities. Moreover, the dynamic capabilities model asserted that the RBV model could not explain "timely responsiveness and rapid and flexible product innovation, along with the management capability to effectively coordinate and redeploy internal and external competences" (Teece & Pisano, 1994, p 537).

The RBV of an organization's response to environmental change is static, while the dynamic capabilities conceptualization of an organization's response to environmental disruption places it in a continuously adapting mode. A framework for understanding the difference between these two environments, one static and the other dynamic, is reflected in a diagram by Breznik and Hisrich (2014) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Key ideas of building the right sources of a firm's success (Breznik & Hisrich, 2014, p. 4).

According to Wang and Ahmed (2006), dynamic capabilities are the organization's behavioral orientation to integrate, reconfigure, recreate, and renew its resources and capabilities continually. Moreover, Wang and Ahmed (2006, p. 35) highlight the crucial organizational ability to reconstruct and upgrade the organization's core capabilities to create and maintain a competitive advantage in response to environmental changes. As a concept, dynamic capabilities are viewed as useful yet limited by a lack of systematic identification and the prevalence of mixed-use interpretation of the theory components. Through a comprehensive study of organizations across many industries and across multiple decades, Wang and Ahmed (2006) constructed a research model of dynamic capabilities, which provides a useful framework for understanding the application of dynamic capabilities within organizations. A distinguishing characteristic of the model is the presence and importance of direct and indirect relationships between dynamic capabilities and market dynamism, firm strategy, capability development, and firm performance. Additionally, the model describes dynamic capabilities' component factors to be applied to all organizations regardless of the industry. The model elucidates the underlying processes that facilitate deployment of dynamic capabilities, providing a useful road map for organizational leaders to understand, develop, and strategize for organizational success within the dynamic capabilities model. In addition, because they face frequent policy changes and may respond to short-term planning horizons, dynamic capabilities may be important for public sector organizations (Pablo, Reay, Dewald & Caceber, 2007).

In addition to the above stated, dynamic capabilities are often considered synonymous with innovation capabilities. Debate over the relationship between the two is robust. At a minimum there are significant commonalities between dynamic and innovation capabilities. The chief intersections are found in the central role of learning, strategic orientation, their heterogeneous nature, the key role of leadership, and the nature of capability development to change, configure, improve, and do something differently (Breznik & Hisrich, 2014).

Organizations' internal resources have a great influence on innovation in industries such as the manufacturing industry. However, the importance of external resources, such as collaboration with external knowledge, as well as customer engagement, has been emphasized in the service industry (Kim, Song & Triche, 2014). It is therefore important to consider both internal and external resources as well as the relationship between the two. Additionally, it is essential to understand the organization-specific dynamic capabilities for the innovation process (Kim et al., 2014). O'Connor (2008) suggests that seven elements are required in order to build dynamic capabilities toward major innovation. These seven elements are: (1) clearly identified organizational structure; (2) internal and external interface mechanisms; (3) exploratory processes; (4) requisite skills; (5) appropriate governance and decision-making mechanisms and criteria; (6) appropriate metrics; and (7) cultural and leadership context (O'Connor, 2008).

Furthermore, Teece et al. (1997) highlight the importance of communication to promote organizational learning, which features two specific characteristics. First, organizational and individual communication skills are necessary as communication is inherently "social". Second, the organizational knowledge generated by the communal sharing of information resides in the organizational interactions such as meetings or other communication channels. At the macro level, organizations can communicate with other actors in their environment through partnerships and collaborations, which can function as a "check" on the organizational communication practices.

Collaborations offer organizations the opportunity to improve or change their communications function for improved operations (Teece et al., 1997; Gomez & Ballard, 2013).

2.2. Shared Leadership and Strategic Shared Leadership

Strategic Leadership is a leadership style that has been proven to support innovative activity within an organization (Rosing, Frese, & Bausch, 2011; Pitelis & Wagner, 2019). It is highly applicable to top managers and boards whose decisions often set the direction for decision making throughout the organization. Shared Leadership is defined as leadership that occurs when a group of individuals lead each other to achieve successful outcomes (Carson, Tesluk, & Marrone, 2007). Sotarauta (2005) asserts that Shared Leadership (SL) for dynamic capabilities is particularly applicable to complex regional development where multiple actors and visions of the future converge in an environment of creative tension. The unique dynamic capabilities of a region are best met with many leaders with previous experience navigating the “riptide” of multiple interests, challenges, and opportunities (Sotarauta, 2005, p.12).

Through Shared Leadership (SL), regional dynamic capabilities can be identified, and the implicit made explicit. Key elements such as innovation capacity and a distinctive knowledge pool can be directed through leadership that utilizes and develops the capabilities of “strategy, interpretation, combination, absorption and excitement” (Sotarauta, 2005, p. 11). This model relies on an investment from a region in fostering leadership to enhance these capabilities. It underscores the central role leaders play in identifying and enhancing dynamic capabilities for the benefit of multiple organizations and actors at the regional level. Sotarauta’s (2005) approach to the relationship between leaders and dynamic capabilities is applicable in instances where a business collaborates with or receives funding from regional or municipal organizations with political representatives.

Strategic Shared Leadership (SSL) is defined as “leadership of the firm, involving the purposeful sharing of strategic decisions, and the process of making and taking these, between the dominant coalition that is initiated and implemented by a focal strategic leader or a small group of strategic leaders such as the CEO and Chair of the Board.” (Pitelis & Wagner, 2019, p. 24). Pitelis and Wagner (2019) identify Shared Strategic Leadership (SSL) as a generator and predictor of dynamic capabilities in an organization due to SSL’s ability to enhance organizational cognition and subsequently enhance Organizational Dynamic Capabilities (ODCs). Pitelis and Wagner (2019) highlight the particular strength that SSL carries to co-create ODCs that can reliably deliver change and notably, do not rely on a single leader’s human and social capital, cognitive abilities or influence.

Strategic Leadership (SL) on its own is viewed as limited by its vulnerability to being personalized and transient in nature. The purposeful sharing of strategic decisions leverages the team’s wisdom and experience and is subject to more checks and balances. Moreover, for the purposes of identifying ODCs, SSL is superior to a strategic charismatic leader whose own personal dynamic capabilities may be insufficient or difficult to separate from ODCs. Here, SSL integrates, transforms and co-creates novel ODCs (Pitelis & Wagner, 2019). SSL addresses each of the Dynamic capabilities’ foundational clusters: Sensing, Seizing and Transforming. SSL is offered as a reliable model for delivering novel ODCs that can deliver change through sensing, seizing and

transforming with greater reliability and can be employed by leaders who identify with other leadership models. Reliable change is an ODC aspect, hence Pitelis and Wagner (2019) submit that SSL enhances ODCs.

Furthermore, Pitelis and Wagner (2019) describe the organizational characteristics of the SSL model as follows:

- 1) A small cohesive top management strategic leadership team.
- 2) A clear focus on sharing strategic decisions, not the day-to-day operations.
- 3) A meticulous, careful selection of team members to minimize groupthink, foster creative dissent and leverage cognitive diversity in regular, meaningful meetings.
- 4) The existence of complementary strategic leadership processes at the Board and CEO level.
- 5) Brainstorming and mutual monitoring practices as a regular part of organizational operations.

Moreover, Pitelis and Wagner (2019) underscore the importance of commitment from top leadership to practice within the model described above. In doing so, the top leadership embeds and institutionalizes the practice which in turn co-creates ODCs. Hence Pitelis & Wagner (2019) conclude that SSL is positively related to the creation of dynamic capabilities.

Both Shared Leadership (SL) and SSL share characteristics of three other leadership theories: Adaptive, Authentic and Situational leadership (Northouse, 2016; Vroom & Jago 2007). Components of these three leadership theories are revealed to be incorporated in the SL and SSL models. Authentic leadership can be defined from an intrapersonal, interpersonal, and developmental perspective. The development perspective as defined by Northouse (2016) best aligns with SL and SSL models. Additionally, SL and SSL feature Adaptive leadership style components such as being follower-centered and emphasizing the leader's ability to help others to work and adapt to changing environments (Northouse, 2016). Lastly, Situational leadership, like SL and SSL considers how leadership is conducted in different situations and how leaders issue directives and support employees (Northouse, 2016). These are all key components to leadership when considering innovation and supporting growth development within an organization or a project (Heaton et al., 2020).

In addition to the above stated, Nonaka, Hirose, & Takeda (2016) assert that to identify new opportunities, an organization must engage in various forms of searching and exploring at the middle and lower leadership levels. This often involves interactions with the environment during the sensing stage of the dynamic capabilities model. Additionally, Nonaka et al. (2016) claim that for an organization to be successful in implementing the dynamic capabilities model, if an organization is structured in a hierarchical manner where most decisions are made by top management, top management must delegate power to lower tiers as well as to empower middle management. This empowerment of middle management must occur as it is middle and lower management who generate knowledge to sense, seize, and transform within the organization. It is therefore important for top management to recognize that they alone cannot promote dynamic capabilities, but rather that they need to distribute leadership where the values, mission, and vision of the organization are infused in all aspects to advance the organization's dynamic capabilities and create value for society. This approach is key to realizing an organization's dynamic capabilities and it has been proven to help drive innovation (Nonaka et al., 2016).

2.3. Consumer value creation

Due to the increasing intensity of competition between businesses and the strong trend toward globalization, the role of the consumer has changed to include cooperation, co-creation of value, and co-development of knowledge and competencies (Martelo, Landroquez, Barroso Castro, & Cepeda-Carrión, 2011). Additionally, these authors point out that a continuously more complex competitive environment has led to an increase in consumers demanding superior value, and hence, to achieve and maintain a competitive advantage, organizations must consider consumer value as a key factor. Consumer value here is understood to mean the satisfaction said consumer experiences, or expects to experience, by taking a given action relative to the cost of that action. Therefore, it can be assumed that organizations should focus on improving capabilities that focus on maximizing the value created for the consumer (Harvard Business Review, 1998).

Such capabilities may include market orientation, knowledge management, and customer relationship management (Martelo et al., 2011). Market orientation is an approach to business that prioritizes identifying the needs and desires of consumers and creating products and services that satisfy them. The aim of market-oriented organizations is to understand both the expressed and unrealized consumer needs and wants and to develop superior solutions to meet them. It is pointed out that organizations are not able to gain competitive advantages solely by meeting the consumer's latent needs but only gain a competitive advantage when the organization is able to meet both the expressed and unrealized consumer needs. This also provides organizations with an opportunity to build strong consumer loyalty (Martelo et al., 2011). Furthermore, Martelo et al. (2011) advise organizations to realize that knowledge is a crucial resource in the current business environment.

Knowledge management is defined as an organization's capture, use, and analysis of the impact of a group's collective knowledge (Martelo et al., 2011). Therefore, there is a need for processes that facilitate both individual and collective knowledge creation, transfer, and leverage. Finally, customer relationship management, understood to be a company's relationships and interactions with customers and potential customers, is essential. It has been previously observed in several sectors that profits drop significantly when the rate of consumer retention and loyalty decreases (Martelo et al., 2011). A combination of these three capabilities and the organization's competitive advantage creates consumer value. Teece et al. (1997) grouped together the sources of competitive advantage into three existing paradigms: competitive forces approach; strategic conflict approach; and the RBV. However, Teece et al. (1997) also identified and described aspects of a new, fourth, paradigm that they labeled 'dynamic capabilities approach' which drives consumer value. This last approach is used to explore the object of the case study.

3. Methodology and methods

In this chapter the research methodology approach and research design are described including the appropriateness of the case study approach for this thesis. The qualitative method, the interpretive approach, and the hybrid research approach, including deductive and inductive coding systems, are outlined. The interview method and participant details, including stakeholder positionality, in relation to the object of the case study are presented in detail. An outline of the validity and reliability best practices that were employed is followed by a description of the research approach to the data analysis and the conceptualization of broad themes used to approach interviewee transcripts.

3.1. Methodology

The research adopts an interpretivist research philosophy grounded in Schultz' (1967) assertion that the interviewer's subjective point of view helps make sense of the research phenomena. As necessary, the second order of understanding phenomena is to employ a theory as a mechanism through which to comprehend the investigated phenomena (Schultz, 1967). As such, the research can be classified as interpretivist because both the researchers' meaning-making and the interviewee data reflect their subjective experiences.

3.2. The Case Study Approach

A case study is an empirical inquiry examining a contemporary phenomenon for the purposes of exploring the relationship between the phenomenon and a real-life context (Yin, 2009). Researchers can gain better understandings of the phenomenon through multiple sources of data collection. In this research project the sources are in the form of historical documentation and interviews. Case studies differ primarily in their methods but share a similar approach to revealing the core essence of a phenomenon (Baxter & Jack, 2008). Investigating a single case was chosen according to Siggelkow (2007) who advocates for persuasive case studies.

3.3. The Application of the Qualitative Method to a Case Study

The qualitative method is appropriate considering the complex and organization-specific nature of dynamic capabilities. Eisenhardt and Martin (2000) identify processes and routines as the foundations of dynamic capabilities, making them best suited to qualitative methodology. This study employs the case study approach based on Yin's (1994) principle of theoretical representativeness for its capacity to illuminate the links between dynamic capabilities in an organization and the development of a social innovation project and leadership behavior.

Qualitative research, according to Van Maanen (1998, p. xi), emphasizes the "flexibility and emergent character" of research design and inquiry with an emphasis on being motivated by theory. "Qualitative work produces narratives – nonfiction division – that link events to events in storied or dramatic form with beginnings, middles, and ends. Story elements are explicitly connected, thus *emplotting* a research report with an apparent causal structure that itself is made theoretically plausible through argument and analogy. There are many narrative forms available to qualitative

researchers. Still, the idea is to create historically situated tales that include both highly focused portraits of what identifiable people in particular places at certain times are doing and a reasoned interpretation for why such conduct is common or not” (Van Maanen, 1998, p. xi-xii, original emphasis).

3.4. Interviews

The interviews conducted for this research study were aimed at exploring the stakeholders’ experiences, both internal and external, in the Bergengborg, Sweden region, the Bergengborghem organization and at TLP. Therefore, the study features a series of open-ended questions designed to explore how leaders experienced and viewed challenges and other stakeholders; how leaders perceived their own roles and understood their responsibilities; the skills utilized in the launching of TLP; and the leaders’ experiences of “learning on the job”. Similarly, open-ended questions were posed to residents themselves to address their experiences thus far with management and their experience in the project itself. At times, rewording of questions allowed for deeper understanding and more reflection on the part of the interviewees.

Seven interviews were conducted involving: one Bergengborgshem board member, the Bergengborgshem CEO, two mid-level managers, the original project director, a program director (host), and two current TLP residents. Interviews via email were conducted with two experts in municipal housing outside of both the project and the Bergengborgshem organization. The criteria for choosing interviewees were based on the TLP project initiation history, originating at the municipal political level and ultimately resulting in hiring a project manager who now works as a mid-level manager at TLP. As TLP is the only multigenerational, intercultural residential facility Bergengborgshem runs, these criteria necessarily limited the number of stakeholders who could be contacted for interviews.

The limited number of available interviewees did, however, ensure a more targeted population. This group included individuals with expertise in their areas and who had experienced the development and launching of TLP from within the organization. Each interviewee could describe their interaction with the innovation process. A few had an understanding of Bergengborghem’s organizational setting in which the decisions that led to the project were made. The sample group is small, but because of their expertise and their long-term involvement with Bergengborghem, their responses were considered adequate in describing the innovation process in the organization to facilitate the novel TLP project. Small sample size, according to Romney, Weller, and Batchelder (1986) is justified if each participant possesses a high degree of expertise on the research topic. The interview results are particular, and therefore, the data cannot be considered as generalizable to all housing organizations, however, they are applicable to the situation studied in the case.

Following a semi-structured design that allows new ideas to emerge in the interview, this research study adopted a set of themes when designing the questions. This approach allows for better exploration of topics without stringently adhering to preconceived concepts. The interviews with either two people at one time or one person alone lasted approximately sixty minutes and were conducted via Microsoft Teams. The researchers recorded each interview, and two interviewers were present for each video interview. The thesis authors conducted the interviews and subsequently transcribed and translated them.

Golden (1992) recommends supplementing primary data gathered from interviews with secondary sources, including organizational brochures, newspaper articles, interviews with appropriate organizational representatives, governance materials, annual reports, and the like to reinforce research validity. Therefore, this research study relied both on interviews and supplemental sources for analysis including the organization’s 2019 and 2020 Sustainability reports and the organization’s website.

3.5. Participants

The interviews with the participants were conducted via Microsoft Teams, Zoom or via email between the 9th of April 2021 and the 5th of May 2021. In total, nine individuals with unique stakeholder positions were interviewed for this study. Table X illustrates the stakeholder positions of each interviewee in relation to the TLP project and to the organization, the duration of the interview, the types of interactions with each stakeholder, and a description of said interactions. It is important to note that Interviewee D was the contact person within the organization and the TLP project which is why the authors of this study communicated more extensively with this interviewee.

Table 1: Overview of all interviewees, how they participated in the study and their position as a stakeholder in relation to TLP.

Interviewee	Stakeholder position	Interview Date	Duration of Interview (transcribed part of interview)	Interaction type and frequency	Interaction Description
A	CEO	09.04.2021	60 min	1 interview via Microsoft Teams 1 Email	Conducted together with Interviewee B
B	Board Member	09.04.2021	60 min	1 interview via Microsoft Teams 1 Email	Conducted together with Interviewee A
C	Host	26.04.2021 04.05.2021	60 min	1 interview via Microsoft Teams 3 Emails	Conducted individually
D	Project manager	26.04.2021	60 min	1 Interview via Zoom 50+ email follow ups 1 Phone call	Conducted individually

				followup 3 Sms followup	
E	Resident	27.04.2021 04.05.2021	45 min	1 interview via Microsoft Teams 3 Emails	Conducted together with Interviewee F Email sent individually
F	Resident	27.04.2021 05.05.2021	45 min	1 interview via Microsoft Teams 4 Emails	Conducted together with Interviewee E Email sent individually
G	Project leader	29.04.2021	60 min	1 interview via Microsoft Teams 2 Email	Conducted individually
H	Municipal Committee member	05.05.2021	20 min	1 interview via email	Conducted individually
I	Other municipal housing official	05.05.2021	20 min	1 interview via email	Conducted individually

3.6. Research design

This research study focuses on an existing framework for understanding a social innovation project within the leadership of a for-profit housing organization. As the research employs the case study approach grounded in Yin's (1994) principle of theoretical representativeness, this paper features a descriptive research design considered to be the most appropriate for investigating leadership and leaders' subjective perceptions of social innovation activities within the dynamic capabilities framework. Our units of analysis began with investigating individuals, processes, and governance structures in the housing organization. A descriptive research design allows researchers to examine leaders' perceptions of the current organizational position and conditions (Knupfer & McLellan, 2001). Researchers conducted semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions in four categories: leadership, and the dynamic capabilities clusters of sensing, seizing, and transforming.

3.7. Data analysis

Inductive strategies were employed through reading interviewee transcripts several times to identify categories and themes, especially in leadership. Through discussion, the researchers considered possible meanings and connections during transcript analyses. The researchers

developed a coding framework based on interviewee responses, and the transcripts were reviewed again using these codes. If new codes emerged, the transcripts were once again re-read according to the amended structure. Categories were developed based on frequency of interviewee references to topics which through this process were then conceptualized into broad themes (Thomas, 2003). Diagrams were developed to focus on the emerging results linking interviewee experiences to unique organizational dynamic capabilities and leadership. Similarities and differences among interviews were explored.

A hybrid research study was employed based on both Boyatzis' (1998), and Crabtree and Miller's (1999) approaches, wherein both inductive and deductive qualitative methods of thematic analysis can be employed. A deductive coding system serves as the analytical base, crafted on an established theoretical framework. The researchers employed the dynamic capabilities theory for the deductive system. At the same time, reviewing the data collected from interviews and secondary materials, important moments were recognized and encoded inductively as described above. This research relied on extant leadership theories connected to dynamic capabilities theory and social innovation in the context of an urban housing organization.

3.8. Reliability and validity

According to Bryman (2005), issues of reliability and validity regarding qualitative research relate to the ability to repeat results of the study and to the integrity of the conclusions generated by the research. As has been mentioned previously, Yin (1994) emphasizes the capacity of qualitative research through the case study to reveal links between a theory and a real-life context. Generalizability is therefore not the goal of a case study, which is difficult to generalize because statistical techniques employed in quantitative research do not apply. This study follows Yin's (2013) key practices for strengthening validity and reliability in a case study. Specifically, the thesis adopts Yin's (2013) suggestion to employ logic models wherein a sequence of transitional conditions explain how a phenomenon or event occurs, adopting arrows that clearly explain how one box leads to another. Additionally, this study follows the recommendations to counteract data falsification through precise transcriptions of interviews facilitated by audio recordings, as well as ensuring the presence of more than one interviewer for increased data reliability (Yin, 2017). Strengthening validity and reliability in a case study through the above practices enables researchers to present in a non-numeric fashion consistent with qualitative research a reliable explanation or theory for an intervention, event or phenomenon and its outcomes (Yin, 2013).

The Appendices of this study include the research descriptions, interviewee rights, and summary of interview questions which were sent to interviewees in advance of the interview. These documents transparently alerted interviewees to the nature of the study, the categories of interview questions and explained the voluntary and anonymous nature of their participation. Following these procedures creates trust between the interviewers and interviewees and limits the possibility of bias (Yin, 2013).

3.9. Limitations

Several limitations have been considered throughout the course of writing this thesis. First, only nine interviews were conducted, which limits the range of the data collected. Additionally, seven of the interviews were conducted via online meeting platforms such as Zoom and Microsoft Teams due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic limiting in-person interactions. The remaining two interviews were conducted via email. The follow-up questions were also sent to the interviewees via email. As the interviews were not conducted in person, the quality of the interviews may be questioned. Misinterpretations can occur under such conditions including disregarding or missing body language, missing information due to external disturbances such as interruptions caused by technological failure or external noises. In order to combat these limitations, interviewees were asked to find a quiet place where they would not be disturbed to conduct the interviews. Additionally, positive aspects of conducting the interviews through online platforms included the interviewees feeling comfortable owing to their being in their known environments, and a greater flexibility for scheduling interviews.

In addition to this, the complex nature of dynamic capabilities and leadership within innovation may not be understood by all the interviewees. In response to this limitation, informational letters were sent to all the interviewees outlining the purpose of the study, how it would be conducted, their rights, as well as information on how to contact the authors of this thesis. Furthermore, the interview guides were also adapted based on the interviewee's stakeholder position. However, it cannot be discounted that the interviewees may have had preconceptions of the concepts or may not have fully understood the concepts involved with this thesis.

Furthermore, the identified themes and patterns in the descriptive analysis are based on the interpretations of the results by the authors of this thesis. Therefore, incorrect conclusions may have been made. However, in an attempt to counteract this and to stay as objective as possible, the results follow the data rather than an opinion. Additionally, to ensure that information is not misconstrued, direct quotes as well as paraphrases are used in the description of the data.

4. Presentation of the object of study

In this chapter, an overview of the case organization, the history of the project origins and criteria for resident project participation is presented.

The Loneliness Project (TLP) is a new (2019) Swedish housing project initiated by Bergenborgshem, the Bergenborg municipality's housing company whose mission is to facilitate social integration among the young and old and the "natively Swedish" and the recently arrived refugee population. The project results from the political will of the Bergenborg region, in which three social sustainability challenges had risen to the top of the agenda (personal communication, April 9, 2021). Of paramount concern was the growing number of young and older residents experiencing involuntary loneliness, with companion challenges of integrating young refugee populations successfully into Swedish society along with offering non-siloed housing opportunities to Bergenborg residents. The project was launched in December of 2019 with just a few months of functioning without the COVID-19 pandemic enforced social distancing rules, making the original project plans of highly interactive living challenging to execute (personal communication, April 9, 2021). As the project was only approved to run for two years, the leadership has requested a one-year delay of the project's evaluation (personal communication, April 9, 2021).

TLP's project aim was to provide novel convivial living through apartments rented to seniors over 70 years of age and an equal number to young adults between 18 and 25. The latter population is comprised of Swedish-born young adults and recently arrived refugee immigrants. Bergenborgshem designed the facilities to foster community through communal kitchens, a fitness room, a library, an art studio, a gaming room, and other functional spaces to be determined among the residents. TLP staff interviewed residents before accepting them. Residents committed to abide by the community living agreements, including agreeing to an obligation to spend time together with subpopulations other than one's own. TLP's website specifies that residents must speak Swedish and, or English and that two hours per week, they must participate in collective activities. Participants must join an all-resident meeting once per month as a form of self-governance. An employee of Bergenborgshem called a "TLPvård" works on site as a host described as a program inspirer and initiator (Bergenborgshem website n.d.).

5. Descriptive analysis

In this chapter the empirical data is presented according to five themes which emerged throughout the interviews. The five identified themes were (1) Politics, Culture and Innovation, (2) Communication and Customer Value, (3) Leadership, (4) Dynamic Capabilities System Clusters: Identifying, Building, and Deploying, (5) COVID-19. The following chapter is therefore organized into sections based on these themes. Finally, a list of key findings that serves as a summary of the analysis will be presented.

5.1. Politics, culture and innovation

5.1.1. Politics

All management agrees that there was political support for this project. Top management identified having to deal more with political agendas than lower management, who said politics was neutral and did not affect the residents. Top management stated:

Yes, but it is like this that politically we have different goals and then the state has adopted the goal that we should be the most innovative state, come up with new things, we should not be afraid to test new things. (Interviewee B)

Meanwhile, lower management claimed:

I do things without thinking about politics. And I try to be neutral there. This is where people live.... So working here, I think it's pretty neutral. (Interviewee C)

5.1.2. Culture

Middle management spoke about the culture within the organization and stated, “We're really transparent.” (Interviewee G).

When speaking about the culture within TLP, middle management said that staff had observed culture shocks between the residents. A middle manager stated:

I asked them about what were, the culture shocks, and they mentioned one, funny thing about the immigrant group, not knowing all the social codes in terms of how to interact with the other residents, because many of them come, or all of them come from the Middle East, where senior citizens in those countries have higher status than here, I'd say. So, there was a quite funny issue connected to that because they didn't want to be rude. So, an older person would start talking to them in the corridor, but they wouldn't tell them that they have a bus to catch. So, they would miss the bus because they felt it would be rude to stop talking to the older members, which is obviously a normal thing to say, ‘I have a bus to catch. Can we continue later on?’ and it wouldn't be an issue. But that was the biggest cultural shock. (Interviewee G)

5.1.3. Innovation

When speaking about innovation, an interviewee mentioned that Bergenborgshem has a tradition of innovation within the organization.

We have a tradition of trying new things, and we have the practical means to do it.
(Interviewee G)

Moreover, Bergenborgshem's 2020 Sustainability report underscores the organization's leadership position regarding innovation in social and environmental sustainability. It was explained by middle and lower management that there is the freedom to innovate within the organization and that this permission and drive to innovate moves the organization forward. This innovation is also in line with the region's political agenda, which the organization helps to achieve. To innovate, Bergenborgshem leadership conduct testing and subsequently, they calculate the risks. The TLP tenants also describe themselves as innovators and lived through the COVID-19 pandemic with a self-described innovative philosophy. External stakeholders have also described Bergenborgshem's innovation culture and also stated that the housing organization takes the lead to inspire other developers.

5.2. Communication and customer value

5.2.1. Communication strategies

Through the interviews it became apparent that each stakeholder had a unique approach to communication strategies and that these different communication strategies depended on the context. Interviewees stated that they were able to adapt their communication styles based on the perceived need. Top management described their routine communications as featuring monthly meetings with the tenants to discuss concerns, ideas, and thoughts. Top management said:

But the flow of information *in* TLP, you can say, it is very important that the housing council, the residents meet every month and decide on, and take up things that work and that do not work. There is a large flow of information. There, we basically get all the development from what they want. (Interviewee A)

Additionally, top management described the information flow within the organization and the idea generation pattern as being both bottom-up and top-down. Employees generate innovative ideas and communicate up to the organizational leadership and then to the Board of Directors who then decide whether to pursue these ideas. The Board subsequently communicates the decisions and the corporate directives down to the lower-level employees.

Also, when it comes to ideas, we work with a bottom-up perspective where very many employees come up with ideas and then we are positive to test but it must still be in... you have to write your hypothesis for what you think, you have to also describe what to test, and one must describe how to evaluate. And then we look at it. If it is within the framework of our assignment, then we take it further and then we also look in competition with others, we have resources that usually work. It is about competence or time that becomes the limitation ... (Interviewee A)

Middle and lower management personnel also described the monthly meetings. However, they added that additional bi-weekly meetings exist for tenants to attend to prepare for the monthly meetings. The monthly and bi-weekly meetings, currently conducted via Teams due to the COVID-19 pandemic, are an opportunity for residents to discuss any issues, to make comments, and to solicit feedback. If there is an issue that needs to be resolved, it is in these meetings that solutions are suggested and voted on by the residents. The host present at TLP said:

Once we have the meetings, house meetings or monthly meetings and two weeks before those, we have a meeting before the meeting, just to pick up if there's something- because I want to be prepared. (Interviewee C)

Middle management emphasized transparency and close contact with the residents, calling it essential. The residents communicated that they felt they were receiving clear, reliable information through the meetings. There has been adequate support and opportunities for all residents to participate in monthly and bi-weekly meetings. The residents added that communication with middle management occurs through the lower management, their host, and online tools. One of the residents of TLP described these meetings as follows:

We take it [issues] up at the monthly meeting, i.e. we have monthly meetings, and we also have two weeks before the monthly meeting, so it is a meeting that anyone can come to and there you make the agenda. And then you can go there, and you have a point and then it comes along. And just like (*the other resident*) says, you have to wait until after... you bring this up at the monthly meeting and then you see what people say and sometimes there are final votes.... so, it's just final votes now. And the decisions are made so you can vote through Facebook and stuff. And then you decide. You don't make a decision without first everyone being able to say what they want to say. (Interviewee F)

External stakeholders confirmed that Bergenborgshem employs skilled leadership to facilitate productive dialogues amongst and with the tenants. Further, they stated that the host often facilitated the discussion or tenants utilized the online tools:

They are hard-working, and how they conduct the dialogues with the tenants- it's impressive. (Interviewee H)

Furthermore, across the Bergenborgshem organization, there is a strong emphasis on dialogue as a central organizational tenet. The organization engages in conversation with heterogeneous stakeholders through multiple channels, including one-on-one meetings with residents, online communication, coffee, and cake pop-up meetings initiated during the pandemic, community discussion forums, industry communication workshops, and in-house employee workshops. All stakeholders, from top managers down to residents themselves, mentioned the importance of transparency in communication.

5.2.2. Customer value

The analysis of Bergenborgshem's TLP tenant communication has revealed an emphasis on and strategy for customer value creation. Top management identified customer value as being primarily

concerned with the social issue of involuntary loneliness. Bergenborgshem's sustainability reports also expressed this sentiment regarding the regional political agenda. Therefore, Bergenborgshem aligned their vision and mission with solving this social issue.

We have a lot of people who live only one person in their apartment and do not meet any other people all day. So that loneliness makes dementia come earlier, loneliness makes you feel insecure and so that.... Creating something that reduces loneliness and creates community has been our focus... (Interviewee A)

However, middle and lower management elaborated upon this to include more specific instances of value created for customers. Many stakeholders revealed that value creation includes:

- Conflict resolution
- Rapid response to residents' concerns
- Identifying and solving issues quickly and easily

Additionally, managers stated that “the concept [of TLP] needs to live up to their [the residents'] expectations.” (Interviewee G). The residents echoed this in their own responses, stating:

We have such a host, who is great. You can text her or sometimes she's here on the spot or in her room. So it's just... If I ever have a problem, I'll write to her. She always answers right away, too. She's good (Interviewee F).

Bergenborgshem's commitment to minimize the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic was found to increase both the means and opportunities for dialogue between residents and employees. The company increased security measures to maintain safety standards. They increased lending opportunities to residents whose income was adversely affected by the pandemic. Management organized courtyard activities to give residents relief from home-bound life resulting from Covid-19 health and safety restrictions. Additionally, they managed summer activities with social distancing in 2020 and online exercise programs. Finally, the Bergenborgshem website added a live chat function to increase customer service and rapid problem-solving capabilities.

5.3. Leadership

During the interviews, researchers asked each participant to describe the leadership styles they implemented themselves and or observed within the organization. The different management levels connected their leadership styles to the organization's values, but each took a unique approach to leadership. Top management described a more guiding and delegating type of leadership, saying: “I have delegated leadership, which right now [results in] a strong project group that runs TLP.” (Interviewee A) and “... both daily operations and the project [itself], are delegated to the project team and to officials working on site.” (Interviewee A).

Middle managers and residents also identified some essential qualities attributable to leadership. These qualities include establishing trust, educating, and empowering leaders, aligning around and being passionate about the vision, being authentic, adapting based on situations, having a common goal to guide, and implementing fair and honest leadership practices. Middle management also

emphasized the importance of agility, stating: “So the personal view of leadership was there; it was agility, a lot of agility as a consequence of the nature [of the project].” (Interviewee D). Another middle manager described empowering and educating employees as follows:

In my opinion, it makes a lot more sense to use your personnel for advanced stuff - as advanced as possible- in order for them to feel happy at work, and to grow as employees. And my job is to give them the opportunity to do just that. I think the more you can empower employees, the better (Interviewee G).

The middle and lower management also expressed a high level of autonomy within the organization and stated: “Well, actually, we have very much autonomy” (Interviewee D). Additionally, when asked to describe traits associated with successful leadership, it was said: “I think everybody can be a project leader.” (Interviewee D). However, at another point, this interviewee added a contradictory qualification to their first statement:

So, it's a combination of leading with the structure and having the feeling for them. So, I think it's a combination of personality and skills, that has to be in that kind of work. Because I think that if there isn't, the same goes for the Host too. If the Host was another type of person, it wouldn't work. (Interviewee D).

In the above statement successful leadership is based on the personality traits of an individual as well as the appropriate skills that the individual has and that it is important to find the right combination of personality traits and skills to fill specific leadership positions.

The residents described their leaders as excellent and active listeners. However, the residents had a hard time identifying the lower management contact and middle management contact at the organization as leaders. When pressed to define who leads, one of the residents said:

We actually have the Host of TLP and the Project Manager as leaders then. But I don't want to say they're leaders either, but they control a little bit like that and help us along (Interviewee E).

The residents said that they felt that they were very democratic and therefore had no formal group leader. However, they did acknowledge that they received guidance from the organization. The residents then described how leaders guided them as follows:

The way the Host leads is to take notice of everyone who lives in the house. Like we said, even the quiet and the more chatty... And that we always have these big meetings with voting... yes. I guess that's the position she's leading from, being [aware] of everyone's opinions (Interviewee E).

The top management, however, disputed this claim of lacking leadership and stated:

In setting the social rules of the game, how it should be together with the tenants, we must lead in it. To put the rules of the game together [for the tenants] because they do not take the lead in it themselves (Interviewee A).

The residents also followed this up by discussing how the residents worked together with the organization to achieve the project goals and stated, “we have a common goal: to try to make this [project] as good as possible.” (Interviewee F).

Top management, board leaders, and external stakeholders emphasized that Bergenborgshem is considered a leader in the housing industry. The organization is characterized as holding a bold vision and taking action in environmental and social sustainability. This organizational identification as being an innovator, and a bold leader, especially regarding social sustainability issues, surfaced in interviews with all stakeholders and was a brand identity throughout the secondary materials analysis.

5.4. Dynamic capabilities system clusters identifying, building, and deploying

5.4.1. Identifying (Sensing)

The top management described how they identified the community's need for a program to combat involuntary loneliness and foster better intercultural and intergenerational relationships. They quickly recognized the emerging TLP concept as achievable within the organization. They realized that they had the means to attempt to address the issues. It was then a question of daring to do so. This social integration concept is an uncommon phenomenon in the Nordics, and Bergenborgshem would be the first in Sweden to launch such a test-innovation social housing project. However, they recognized the need to innovate to solve the social issues of both loneliness and integration.

We wanted to try something new here, especially to increase community and understanding in the middle age categories. And since then, we have also taken on, in this project, unaccompanied refugee children (Interviewee B).

Middle management emphasized that the main struggle in the identifying (sensing) cluster was getting people to believe in the idea and consider it viable. Additionally, early on, there was a need to continually evolve and change how the project team was doing things to optimize the team's functional capacity. They also emphasized that it was crucial to have frequent contact with the residents to sense new ideas and opportunities. They accomplished this by getting to know them and observing and actively listening to them.

It was very important for me to get to know the tenants. So, I could just listen to what do they want? What do they feel is good or bad or important? And when I got that feeling, then I could push forward a little bit harder. (Interviewee C).

If I see something, or I want to try something, or if I hear some of the tenants talking about something I start with talking about it with people. Here at TLP- I talked to my boss a lot, and The Project manager is one main person that I always speak to. So just to get it [the resident ideas] out there (Interviewee C).

The residents agreed with this characterization. Furthermore, all levels of managers expressed that there is a solid organizational identity connected with being innovative. Therefore,

Bergenborgshem employees claim that they are more inclined to seek out opportunities for innovation. Moreover, external stakeholders identified the meetings and dialogues with the customers as ideal identifying opportunities. Lastly, Bergenborgshem engages frequently and directly with innovation groups and innovation hubs to stay current with the possibilities and needs of the surrounding community at any given moment. The 2020 Sustainability report states that:

“[Identifying] social conditions - social sustainability - is a natural starting point in Bergenborgshem's business model.”

5.4.2. Building (Seizing)

Top management emphasized that the project group and the organization are continuously looking to identify and quickly build new opportunities. However, despite this, they said it is also important to “not have too many balls in the air” and focus on current projects to ensure that they are thriving instead of continuously adding new projects. Top management also expressed that it is essential to look at the entire region's needs and even to the whole country and forecast what the next ten years may look like to build new opportunities.

So, the whole of southern Sweden, Skåne, Blekinge, and a bit up the country for example, what does the population forecast look like? Will the population increase and how much? What is required? What type of housing is required? What is the age structure like in 10 years? We are now talking about TLP, we know that more and more people are getting older and above all that we are getting older as well! Then a new type of need is created for the elderly, housing for the elderly ... So, it is very important to have very good external monitoring, both in the region, the city, and Bergenborgshem. And this goes together well in terms of the details. Then when it comes down to the level of detail, we build housing that is adapted to the time we live in now, so to speak (Interviewee B).

Additionally, it is essential to remember that the housing industry is a long-term industry and that projects will not generate immediate results for analysis. Top management was optimistic about new ideas and expressed an openness to engage with multiple stakeholders to succeed with new projects when aligned with organizational and community social, environmental, and demographic targets. They stated: “I am positive to new opportunities, and I am positive and look at new ways and new things that appear” (Interviewee A). Being brave was described as essential when building these new opportunities and that the driving force behind building these opportunities should be tackling the identified social problems.

So the driving force is community... [going back to] the loneliness [issue]...[our goal was] to create conditions for meetings and create community- it is of course the biggest driving force for me to remove the loneliness (Interviewee A).

Middle management, however, experienced a struggle getting people to believe in the TLP project. However, once the idea had started to be implemented and small things were starting to happen, people slowly started to believe in the project. Middle and lower management described having to be persistent and strong in their beliefs to push the concept through and make others believe in it too.

Additionally, the residents described how they are also building opportunities and that there are also consumer-led and consumer-executed projects within TLP.

I just want to add that this sewing room thing, it was actually tenants themselves who converted and executed it there (Interviewee E).

The research revealed organization-wide building habits, including adopting new industry criteria for environmental sustainability with an emphasis on data-driven practices and decision making for the care and improvement of real estate and to respond to customer needs. There is a practice throughout the organization for investing in testing for organizational improvements and innovations.

5.4.3. Deploying (Transforming)

When discussing deploying, top management stated that there had only been a few conflicts regarding the launching and early phase of TLP. They had easily resolved these minor issues quickly. Top management's problems were not between employees but rather between the tenants themselves. These tenant issues were managed well by the on-site host. Host success has led to top management electing to transform the original plan to remove the TLP host. Middle and top management changed their opinion of the need for a host based on the residents' feedback and lower management's experience. They revised the project to include having personnel available on-site in the future as well. Top management also stated that a way in which they aim to transform the organization is through daring to say "yes" to new ideas and opportunities.

Another area of deployment identified by middle and lower management was when they identified the need to modify the elder to young ratio in the house and consider personality types when selecting the tenants. Learning from current management experience and through frequent open dialogue with residents they stated:

We have thought about maybe modifying the number of the elderly versus the youngsters, we have also thought about how important it is [to consider] that people may be much, shyer, and not so outgoing (Interviewee D).

Furthermore, management will consider some physical changes to the building and the layout for future TLP projects. Additionally, middle management stated that the management group is only implementing changes requested by the tenants at this stage in the innovation process.

It's very dangerous to change the premises all the time and put new things in all the time if they're not coming up as a need. So, we are not pushing for new things (Interviewee D).

Top management shared that some of the biggest lessons they learned were that it is possible to have a 50-person functioning democracy in a residential housing project. In the future, it would be best to have a larger project group to avoid the project leaders becoming too intertwined with the project.

It is possible to have a direct democracy with 50 people. I did not think it would be so. I've learned that. I thought you would need to put some kind of representation board or something like this, or a little smaller group that would represent the tenants, but everyone is involved [at TLP]. You have a direct democracy that is completely unique. There I learned something (Interviewee A).

Top and middle management identified barriers, including the apartment rental fees and COVID-19 pandemic challenges that hinder project functions and progress. Because one of the main components, socializing, is not possible due to the nationally implemented restrictions, it has been impossible to evaluate the project. Organizational and project transformations related to the COVID-19 pandemic are described in the section below.

5.5. COVID-19

As previously mentioned, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the progress of the TLP project. One of the most significant barriers that TLP has had to face has been the disruption of the project's socialization model, leading to the project testing and evaluation delay. At the same time, the residents have developed a different closeness due to the extraordinary impact of the pandemic.

The evaluation of the project will move forward [to a later date] because of the pandemic. But why I mention it now is because I think we did not know that the pandemic would come, but I think this particular project [in the face of the pandemic]...it has created even more dynamism in a way. Because of the pandemic, we really need each other now in these times (Interviewee B).

Consequently, according to middle management, there has been an obligatory shift in the leadership mindset away from a group focus and onto an individual focus. The change in communication channels has increased one-on-one customer interactions and service. The residents expressed deep disappointment about the COVID-19 restrictions. However, they also complimented Bergenborgshem leadership regarding their efforts to transition from in-person interactions to digital alternatives as seamlessly as possible. Middle management stated that there was initially some frustration from the elderly tenants who lacked technological skills. Thus, the organization invested time into training older residents in the digital solutions adopted by Bergenborgshem to maintain customer interactions. This effort has subsequently resulted in an overall increase in customer satisfaction.

Well, we didn't have a lot of technology before COVID, but now it's become this thing with Teams we use. First, we used Facebook and then it became Teams (Interviewee E).

Across Bergenborgshem's properties, customers kept in contact with the organization through increased digital solutions such as online exercise classes, a live chat feature on the website for fast customer response, online house meetings, and one-on-one video meetings with personnel via Microsoft TEAMS. Additionally, Bergenborgshem provided weekly opportunities for residents to meet outside with personnel for cake and coffee to generate innovative solutions to the evolving COVID-19 challenges. They also organized courtyard activities, entertainment, grocery pickup for

home-bound residents, extended loan opportunities to customers experiencing economic hardship, summer activities for children, and organized a collaborative safety program to fight domestic violence locally. Bergenborgshem increased their local engagement and specifically increased customer dialogue and safety services in more security personnel and longer hours (Bergenborgshem website, 2021).

5.6. Summary of analysis

In this section the key findings of the previous sections are presented. Using these key findings, the framework created by Heaton et al. (2020) was adapted and will be presented below.

5.6.1. Politics, culture, and innovation:

Bergenborgshem has a tradition of innovation throughout the organization, this was confirmed by all levels of leadership within the organization, the residents, and external stakeholders. This aligns with the regional political agenda that places a high degree of importance on being a national leader in innovation.

Regarding politics the research found political alignment across heterogeneous stakeholders. Moreover, Bergenborgshem takes collaborative action on shared socio-political goals. The TLP housing project is an example of this process; the project's origins were at the municipal level and aligned with the organization's goals and competencies. Furthermore, leadership who are mandated to connect regional political and social needs to the organization's activities supported the project. Yet middle and lower management did not report any negative political influence. While the region's politics drove the innovative actions of Bergenborgshem, TLP managers have felt free to lead as they see fit. Residents and lower and middle-level managers reported that their leadership is without outside political interruption or influence. Finally, leaders reported experiencing the freedom to act according to their organizational roles with a sense of alignment with the municipal and regional political and social agendas.

5.6.2. Communication and customer value:

The research showed Bergenborgshem's substantial organizational emphasis on multiple stakeholder dialogue. Top, middle, and lower management described having both top-down and bottom-up communication within the organization. Internal and external stakeholders confirmed that there were clear, transparent, and frequent communication channels. Organizational emphasis on communication was revealed to drive frequent dialogue with customers which was directly connected to creating customer value in the form of conflict resolution, rapid response to residents' concerns, and identifying and solving issues.

5.6.3. Leadership:

Top, middle, and lower management connected their leadership styles to the organization's values. However, there was a difference in leadership style according to the level of the leader, where middle and lower management presented with Shared Leadership styles, while top management displayed more Strategic Shared Leadership (SSL). Additionally, middle and lower management conveyed that they experienced a high level of autonomy and top management conveyed that they

accept a variety of personalities amongst the middle and lower management which is evidence of the structural flexibility. Lastly, internal and external stakeholders agree that the organization itself is a leader within innovation in sustainability regionally and within the housing industry.

5.6.4. Dynamic capabilities and system clusters:

Top management described identifying the need, allocating resources to build the program, followed by deploying their resources and capabilities to meet the challenge/opportunity. Top management is responsible for identifying regional opportunities and needs. Meanwhile, middle management is responsible for identifying appropriate personnel to manage and run the project. Lastly, lower management is responsible for identifying potential issues and opportunities through dialogue with the residents. As for the building cluster, top management is careful when selecting opportunities to allocate resources to and ensure that the opportunity matches with the long-term goals of both the organization and the region's political goals. The building cluster for middle and lower management is concerned with being discretionary when choosing the components for which they seek resources. Lastly, when deploying, top management based the decision to go forward with the project based on an analysis of the long-term goals of the political region as well as the organization and that the organization already had the required resources available for this project. When deploying, the middle and lower management must be very sensitive to the needs of the residents and being able to meet said needs, while not changing the project too much. It was stated that the only changes being deployed by middle and lower management were changes explicitly requested by the residents.

5.6.5. COVID-19:

COVID-19 affected all three dynamic capabilities clusters as it introduced a whole new, and unforeseen, set of challenges to the project. Furthermore, according to middle management, there has been an obligatory shift in leadership focus from a group perspective to a one-to-one perspective. The research revealed new ways in which leaders could identify, build, and deploy. Examples of these shifts were found among top leaders who identified the need to delay the project evaluation for another year, building digital alternatives to in-person social models, and deploying new one-to-one focused communication channels between leadership and the residents. Many customers focused innovations were created by Bergenborgshem to maintain the tradition of close dialogue with customers.

5.6.6. Frameworks:

Figure 2: Systems-level view of dynamic capabilities and campus innovation activities (Heaton et al., 2020)

As discussed in the Theory chapter, Heaton et al.'s (2020) systems-level view of dynamic capabilities presented in Figure 2 offers a framework for understanding dynamic capabilities and leadership in the Bergenborgshem TLP project. The framework is a guide for what Heaton et al. (2020) calls evolutionary fitness, the ability of an organization to anticipate changes affecting their operations, iterate to face them and create value to maintain competitive advantage. Figure 3 is a road map for leadership whose interests include innovation. The model was designed to address innovation at the organizational, industry and regional level and was therefore deemed suitable for the object of the case study whose activities can be viewed from these same perspectives. The diagram of the framework includes the ecosystem in which the organization acts and implies that leaders drive the action in the model.

However, the research conducted on the TLP project revealed the key role that leaders play in activating and enhancing the dynamic capabilities framework. Hence to reflect the findings described in the sections above, the adapted systems level model in Figure 3 includes leaders as actors. Another derivation in Figure 3 is the description of the environment in which leaders act. The case research revealed both micro and macro environments according to the level of leader. Top leaders were found to respond to the macro environment with strategic shared leadership while middle and lower managers interacted more with the micro-environment in a shared leadership style.

As will be elaborated upon in the discussion section that follows, these leaders engage with the organization's unique dynamic capabilities in three identified ways. Where the Heaton et al. (2020) model defines the clusters as sensing, seizing, and transforming, the TLP dynamic capabilities model reflects the findings from the research with terminology deemed most relevant to the case organization's operations. Therefore, the leaders act to *identify*, *build*, and *deploy* the unique

dynamic capabilities revealed through the analysis. Finally, the adapted framework links leaders through the unique dynamic capabilities to the creation of value for customers.

Figure 3: Adapted Dynamic Capabilities Framework-System-level view of TLP

6. Results and discussion

This chapter synthesizes the empirical data from the case study outlined in the findings sections and how these findings answer the research questions. The purpose of this research project was to discover and explore the dynamic capabilities of a social sustainability-oriented housing project and the role of leadership in identifying, building, and deploying these capabilities in the face of the COVID-19 global pandemic. Findings are connected to the literature presented in the Theoretical Background chapter and the two research questions presented in the section: Aim. Each research question will be addressed, followed by discussing the key components and characteristics of the findings.

6.1. Research question 1:

“What are the case housing company’s dynamic capabilities in the context of COVID-19 global pandemic challenges?”

Adapted Dynamic Capabilities Framework- System-level view of TLP (Figure 3) describes the main research findings and their interactions based on the theoretical guidelines of Heaton et al. (2020) dynamic capabilities framework (Figure 2). Where Heaton et al. (2020) includes the ecosystem in which the organization operates, research into Bergenborgshem revealed two distinct environments rather than a general ecosystem. Therefore, the adapted framework distinguishes between the micro-environment with which middle and lower managers interact and the macro-environment with which top managers engage. Moreover, the Heaton et al. (2020) model does not indicate action or direct relationships between clusters in the diagram. Yin (2013) asserts that empirical studies should explain the action between boxes in diagrams to indicate relationships in any analysis. Therefore, the adapted framework both adheres to Yin’s (2013) best practices for research and offers a clearer system-level view for understanding dynamic capabilities.

Heaton et al. (2020)’s model leaves out the leader as a dynamic capability and does not include the leaders as actors within the system. Based on the research findings of this study, leaders are found to be a critical dynamic capability as well as the instigators of action in the three clusters of identifying, building, and deploying for innovation. Teece et al. (1997) states that dynamic capabilities are unique and heterogeneous. They are the organization’s ability to “integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external competencies to address rapidly changing environments.” (Heaton et al., 2020, p. 6). Therefore, inquiry is required to discern what capability an organization most relies on to accomplish its goals, create and capture value and maintain or create competitive advantage (Helfat & Peteraf, 2009). The adapted system-level framework clearly identifies the relationship between leaders, dynamic capabilities and value creation as was revealed through the research findings at Bergenborgshem.

Top managers explained that they were more sensitive to long-term strategic goals according to the politics and demographic trends in the region. Activity in the macro environments sets the dynamic capabilities system into motion by identifying, building, and deploying the identified core capabilities. Similarly, TLP’s host and project manager, labeled as ‘middle managers’, emphasized their strong focus on residents and how changes in resident lives affect the project and activate the same clusters of identifying, building, and deploying.

This study's conceptual framework also emphasizes the role of leaders in connection to the dynamic capabilities system. The importance of leaders as actors within the system addresses the research gap identified in the literature review. Other dynamic capabilities researchers (Sotarauta, 2005) confirm the need for further research emphasizing the role of leaders in the theoretical framework. The study results indicate that the dynamic capabilities that enable TLP and Bergenborgshem to meet the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic rely on leaders to activate the clusters of activity around the four main capabilities. Heaton et al. (2020) confirms the role of leaders, especially those skilled at identifying and convincing others to build and deploy resources based on the identified opportunities or threats. The inclusion of the micro and macro environments in the framework addresses the multiple influences of the ecosystem in which TLP and Bergenborgshem conduct their business activities categorizing them in meaningful ways and connecting them to specific leadership levels. The framework therefore connects environmental factors like the unprecedented global events like the Covid-19 pandemic to the activities and leadership within the organization.

Authors Schoemaker et al. (2018, p. 28) also support the system-level view of dynamic capabilities with an understanding of the role leaders play is essential to understand organizational behavior in the face of extreme threat: "Dynamic capabilities, business model renewal, and leadership must be tightly connected to produce the kind of product, process, and commercial innovations that VUCA (*extreme threat, sic*) conditions demand. Being vigilant and prepared will give a firm its best chance to respond adroitly to challenges and opportunities that may arise, as well as to reshape the broader environment to its own advantage when and where possible."

The context for this research was the COVID-19 pandemic which, through the dynamic capabilities lens is considered to be a significant threat and was also described by Bergenborgshem internal and external stakeholders as a substantial challenge for TLP. In this context, the thesis inquiry revealed TLP's core dynamic capabilities to be:

1. Skilled and appropriate leaders across all levels of leadership and management.
2. Culture of Innovation.
3. Flexible Leadership Structure.
4. Reliable, transparent, and multi-channeled communication practices.

COVID-19 challenges presented an opportunity to analyze and identify the core dynamic capabilities. These core capabilities were already in place at TLP when COVID-19 challenges emerged in Sweden. Therefore, the technological, physical, and organizational changes and innovations necessary to run the program were more easily managed, according to the research results.

Furthermore, Wang and Ahmed (2006) connect the organization with both internal strategy and external environments in their framework for dynamic capabilities. This framework includes the organization's dynamic capabilities in relation to the organization's strategies in order to help the leaders to understand, develop, and strategize for the success of the organization within this dynamic capabilities model. Additionally, Wang and Ahmed (2006) highlight the regenerative quality of the dynamic capabilities model. Bergenborgshem demonstrated a strong awareness of both internal and external environmental factors through frequent stakeholder dialogue. Furthermore, Bergenborgshem also revealed their regenerative dynamic capabilities through

organizational communication practices. This can be further connected with the TLP’s core dynamic capability: Reliable, transparent, and multi-channeled communication practices.

Moreover, to further support the research findings and place them in dynamic capabilities discourse, O’Connor’s (2008) seven elements required to build dynamic capabilities toward major innovation are relevant. Of these seven identified elements, element (2) internal and external interface mechanism can be connected to TLP’s ‘Reliable, transparent, and multi-channeled communication practices’, element (7) cultural and leadership context relates to TLP’s ‘Culture of Innovation’, and elements (4) requisite skills, (5) appropriate governance and decision-making mechanisms and criteria (6) appropriate metrics and (7) cultural and leadership context reflect TLP’s ‘Skilled and appropriate leaders across all levels of leadership and management’. Meanwhile, the element (1) clearly identified organizational structure relates to TLP’s Flexible Leadership Structure. (See Table (2) below)

Table 2: Comparison of O’Connor (2008) elements for innovation with TLP’s unique dynamic capabilities.

TLP’s unique Dynamic Capabilities	O’Connor (2008) elements for major innovation
Skilled and appropriate leaders across all levels of leadership and management.	(3) exploratory processes; (4) requisite skills; (5) appropriate governance and decision-making mechanisms and criteria; (6) appropriate metrics; (7) cultural and leadership context
Culture of Innovation.	(7) cultural and leadership context
Flexible Leadership Structure.	(1) clearly identified organizational structure;
Reliable, transparent, and multi-channeled communication practices.	(2) internal and external interface mechanisms;

6.2. Research question 2:

“How are dynamic capabilities identified, built, and deployed by leadership in a social sustainability-oriented residential housing project in the context of COVID-19?”

The four unique dynamic capabilities identified in Bergenborgshem, as stated in the section above: Research Question 1, are described in detail with specific attention to the connection to leadership. While the Adapted System-level framework in Figure 3 describes the relationships between dynamic capabilities, leaders and value, a further discussion on how leaders identify, build, and deploy using the unique dynamic capabilities is offered in this section.

6.2.1. Skilled appropriate leaders

Leadership for innovation in the face of business disruption surfaced as a critical topic from the interview results. This study's findings confirmed research literature on the importance of innovation to face exogenous crises (Teece et al., 1997). Moreover, marshaling resources to innovate quickly was found to occur throughout the organization at every leadership level. Bergenborgshem was found to place decisive importance on leadership, clearly connecting it to creating value and maintaining competitive advantage. Substantial resource investments to develop and support leaders and top management practices of communicating clearly and frequently with middle and lower-level managers were revealed and confirmed by both internal and external stakeholder interviews. While consistency in leadership for innovation was apparent across all aspects of the organization's activities and communications, approaches to leadership, in general, were less consistent.

Despite these different approaches, this study identified Shared Leadership as the primary model employed throughout the organization at all levels of leadership. An example of shared leadership is Bergenborgshem leaders actively contending with complex regional developments to expand their innovation capacity through collaborations (Sotarauta, 2005). Sotarauta (2005) underscores that leaders play a central role in identifying and enhancing the dynamic capabilities of an organization and the region. The results show that the leaders of Bergenborgshem are all driven to achieve not only their personal goals and the organizational goals but also the regional goals. Additionally, Sotaraunta's (2005) model of Shared Leadership applies to the leadership at Bergenborgshem as the organization is semi-public and collaborates with the municipality and the board is comprised of political representatives.

Pitelis & Wagner (2019) propose that the purposeful sharing of strategic decisions in the Strategic Shared Leadership (SSL) model leverages the subordinate strategic teams' collective knowledge, producing better-informed choices. This study found TLP leadership fit this model. Top leadership, the CEO and Board, strategically share the decision-making process with subordinates, activating the dynamic capabilities framework to improve organizational results. A vital component of the SSL model revealed in the interviews with Bergenborgshem is fostering and valuing creative dissent and the freedom for middle and lower-level managers to have strong personalities, visions, and passion for their projects (Janis, 1972; Pitelis & Wagner 2019). Through interviews, top leadership confirmed their support of middle and lower-level project managers being "bold" and "passionate". Heaton et al. (2020) reveals the importance of leadership with three critical components: (1) leadership and management are deemed essential for value creation; (2) managerial and leadership emotional intelligence; and (3) leadership skills such as coping with change, setting direction, and aligning people with opportunities, empowering, motivating, and connecting people through networks.

Lastly, the Bergenborgshem research confirmed Heaton et al.'s (2020) emphasis on organizational leadership supporting "bold moves" to advance innovation and thereby enhance the evolutionary fitness of the organization. Interviews with top managers at Bergenborgshem confirmed their strategy of encouraging and supporting middle and lower managers with a variety of personalities including those with strong passion to champion innovations such as TLP.

6.2.2. Culture of innovation

Heaton et al. (2020, p. 11) states that the “most powerful transformational lever is an organization’s culture... comprised of norms, values, beliefs, and expectations of organizational members.” Furthermore, the Heaton et al. (2020) dynamic capabilities framework features innovative culture as an essential component of the “sensing, seizing, transforming” clusters for capturing value. This research study confirmed the importance of this capability through numerous reports from interviewees on the significance of “being an innovative organization” when considering Bergenborgshem’s reputation and projects. One example of this was expressed in an external stakeholder who stated, “my impression is that they [*Bergenborgshem*] really live innovation and try to become better constantly.”

Moreover, Bergenborgshem’s organizational culture of innovation is one of the most prominent dynamic capabilities this research uncovered as nearly every interviewee characterized the organization as “innovative”. In order for an organization to be characterized as “innovative” Breznik and Hisrich (2014) assert that they must demonstrate a focus on the role of learning, have a strategic orientation, feature leadership as a crucial organizational competency, and show an ability to improve and innovate in the face of change. Together these characteristics are innovation capabilities or dynamic capabilities. Bergenborgshem demonstrated the above characteristics and therefore fit the definition for being innovative. Without an integrated innovation identity and organizational processes for carrying out innovation, other dynamic capabilities would likely not produce the same results. Heaton et al. (2020) state that “bold moves” must sometimes be supported by leaders to preserve “evolutionary fitness”. In other words, a culture of innovation supports the entire premise of the dynamic capabilities framework, which is based on the concept that organizations must constantly innovate in the face of environmental disruption (Teece et al., 1997). Furthermore, the study found that this culture of innovation was not limited to the organization itself but was also a political agenda for the region, which had a mission to become the most innovative region in Sweden. As Bergenborgshem is a semi-public organization and has set the goal to help the state reach the regional aims, it is only natural that innovation should become part of the organizational culture (*Interview CEO, Board, April 9, 2021*).

A culture of innovation was found to empower leaders within the organization to take bold action which drove social innovation projects such as TLP. Top managers mentioned being proud of the organization for both taking and supporting bold action in the social innovation arena regionally. This supports the European Commission’s Innovation position advocating for social innovation to solve sustainability challenges (European Commission, 2021). Through the study interviews, both internal and external stakeholders stated that they consider Bergenborgshem innovative and confirm the organization offers reliable, transparent communication through multiple channels. These channels were identified to include internal and external meetings, workshops and events, websites, social media, and printed communications materials among and between employees and customers and among and between industry colleagues.

Similarly, as indicated in Figure 3, the projects’ dynamic capabilities leveraged to face the COVID-19 pandemic, the research revealed evidence of the significant role of leaders to activate these clusters. Additionally, the study results connected the relationship between leadership, dynamic capabilities for innovation, and project adaptation in the face of unprecedented challenges resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic. Several connections between leadership and dynamic capabilities

became apparent through the research and interview process. The research results revealed great consistency across the organization regarding the role of innovation generally in the organization and specifically in response to COVID-19 challenges. Both internal and external stakeholders reported that Bergenborgshem has a strong reputation for being innovative, especially in social innovation. Moreover, research revealed heterogeneous stakeholder agreement that leadership encourages and supports innovation.

6.2.3. Reliable Communication

Nonaka et al. (2016) highlights the central role that middle managers play in knowledge creation to advance value creation. According to this research study's observations the TLP innovation process relies on effective communication between teams, managers, and the residents. TLP leaders, residents, and stakeholders outside the organization characterize communication throughout the organization as reliable, transparent with multiple channels available for interaction. Examples of this include frequent internal meetings for top, middle and lower managers to share the knowledge gathered from the regular monthly resident meetings, skillfully facilitated by the TLP host, and reports from stakeholders that the organization places a high value on transparency. The relevance of these findings is confirmed by Martelo et al. (2011) who state that knowledge management and customer relationship management, such as between TLP residents and lower managers, are two of the three capabilities identified in creating an organization's competitive advantage and customer value.

Examples of the communication connection to customer value at TLP include leaders quickly addressing the COVID-19 pandemic challenges of converting in-person activities to digital platforms across all levels of communication. Additionally, management replaced group gatherings with remote presence gatherings, and they replaced in-person meetings with virtual meetings through online channels such as Facebook and Microsoft Teams. Lastly, the Bergenborgshem website added a chat function for immediate responses to customer issues.

The connection between communication and customer value was among the most robust results of this study. COVID-19 challenges tested Bergenborgshem's ability to deliver its innovative housing project. The pandemic limited the core components: shared togetherness spaces and group meetings. However, the organization's commitment to deliver the project as promised to residents drove leaders at all levels of the organization to innovate to approximate the intended experience. TLP leaders have thus far succeeded in increasing their residents' satisfaction throughout the COVID-19 challenges through frequent communication with residents via one-on-one interactions and remote presence experiences.

Research revealed the cohesive nature of communication throughout Bergenborgshem and the TLP project itself. Residents and managers reported that they are aware of and use multiple channels for communication. Moreover, throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, residents feel leadership addresses their concerns rapidly and thoroughly. They report that leadership is transparent, features skilled facilitators, and is highly reliable.

Two themes specifically stood out regarding communication and innovation. First, Bergenborgshem has a solid organizational culture and identification with innovation for social good, which permeates all communication with stakeholders. Across internal and external

stakeholder interviews, the comments on the heart of Bergenborgshem culture were consistent: the TLP project represents the organization's culture of innovation and the social sustainability mission. Second, Bergenborgshem's commitment to dialogue with customers to deliver value is consistent with all interviewee experience. For Bergenborgshem and the TLP project, both customer value delivery and innovation begin with stakeholder dialogue. Within the TLP project, frequent authentic communication with residents led to innovation. Input from the residents drives change within TLP. The research results revealed that communication flows easily due to a high level of trust between the host, leadership, and the residents. Managers built this trust through consistently high levels of customer service and delivery of the original program description. Proven to be reliable, the TLP host gained residents' confidence. The host could quickly adjust, iterate and respond to their needs which is an essential component of innovation in the face of disruption. Middle and lower managers also expressed confidence in their communication channels and the freedom to speak their minds. Lower-level managers expressly confirm that they can interact with middle management on behalf of the customers rapidly and efficiently.

6.2.4. Flexible Leadership Structure

The leadership structure of Bergenborgshem is hierarchical, with all levels of management having discrete activities. Pitelis & Wagner's (2019) characteristics for Strategic Shared Leadership (SSL), as described in the Theoretical Background are highly relevant when considering the hierarchical structure of Bergenborgshem. Bergenborgshem has a small, cohesive top management team that works for strategic leadership. This top management group consists of the board members and the CEO. Furthermore, there is a clear focus on sharing strategic decisions, and the top management focuses on the macro-environment. In contrast, the middle and lower management focuses on the micro-environment and the project's day-to-day operations. Nonaka et al. (2016) findings confirm the SSL structure highlighting the importance of top management setting the "universal vision" of the organization while allowing employees to use their own judgement for projects. This is consistent with the research findings for Bergenborgshem's operations. Frontline workers whose tacit knowledge and frequent customer interaction must be captured to convert it to value, rely upon middle managers to orient the knowledge to the more considerable organizational capabilities. TLP middle and lower-level managers confirmed through their interviews that they experience high levels of autonomy within their job functions.

The third characteristic from Pitelis & Wagner (2019) describes a meticulous selection of team members. When discussing the project team and the selection of the residents, all interviewees expressed a careful selection process involved with the TLP project. The residents described a lengthy interview process conducted by the project team to attempt to find the best combination of residents for TLP. Additionally, when speaking about the selection process for the project team, middle managers stated that it was imperative to consider different skills and personality traits. Therefore, top and middle management closely matched employee skills with project roles.

The fourth characteristic outlined by Pitelis & Wagner (2019) considers the importance of top leadership having their own processes for setting the course and defining the organization's overall vision. The research confirmed this characteristic through interviews with the board and CEO at Bergenborgshem. Top leadership described their focus through regular board meetings as being concerned with regional and national demographic trends, big picture topics always with long-term strategy in mind. The CEO specifically described their role as strategically oriented, stating that

they were not focused on the organization's day-to-day operations. Finally, the 2020 Bergenborgshem Sustainability Report outlined the many collaborations with other outside organizations for innovation. These collaborations are the result of top leadership decisions made at the board and CEO level through their regular meeting structures.

Finally, when considering Pitelis & Wagner's (2019) fifth characteristic, it is clear from interviews that brainstorming and mutual monitoring practices are in place and are a regular part of organizational practices at Bergenborgshem. Mutual monitoring is part of the bi-weekly meetings between the host at TLP and the residents and monthly meetings between the project team and the TLP residents. The information gathered from these meetings is then further communicated upwards within the Bergenborgshem organization to middle and top management. The size and scope of a problem determine where it will be directed for resolution within the organization. Additionally, through the study interviews, it was revealed that there are strict guidelines for the types of issues that top management will handle.

7. Conclusion

This chapter offers insights on the future recommendations for both academia as well as practitioners. This chapter will finish with a section summarizing the thesis, bringing together the unique findings, how these findings align with the aim and what contribution the answers to the research questions provide.

7.1. Future Recommendations

After analyzing Bergenborgshem's TLP social innovation project applying the adapted dynamic capabilities framework (see Figure 3), the results demonstrated that this new framework assists in connecting the discoverable dynamic capabilities to the actions of leaders at different levels of the organization. Moreover, the connection between value creation and leaders' actions is made more visible through applying this framework. The framework applied to the case organization revealed the role that leaders play in enhancing organizational dynamic capabilities. This thesis can therefore be viewed as a first study supporting the usefulness of the adapted framework for illuminating the role of leaders and their key interactions with dynamic capabilities to create value. Therefore, several academic and practitioner recommendations and implications follow.

7.1.1. Implications and Future Recommendations for Academia

The paper contributes to the dynamic capabilities, leadership, and social innovation literatures. Empirical studies such as the housing case examined herein can connect the discourses. This thesis strongly emphasizes the role that leaders play in the dynamic capabilities system and offers a timely acknowledgment of this role in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic disruption. It also highlights dynamic capabilities' relevance as a framework for considering social innovation project design and strategy. An organization's unique and most vital dynamic capabilities govern its evolutionary fitness (Heaton et al., 2020) all of which relies on leaders.

There are several possible future recommendations applicable to academia based on the findings of this thesis. An examination of Bergenborgshem from the tenant perspective in which more abstract questions regarding their observations and experiences with leadership and dynamic capabilities could produce interesting results. Additionally, different approaches to the research could be taken including a quantitative approach which would generate another level of understanding about the application of dynamic capabilities within the case organization. Furthermore, investigating the case organization, their leadership practices, and dynamic capabilities in a different context, or comparing the 2015 immigrant migration crisis to the COVID-19 crisis would also generate greater understanding of the relationship between the leadership and dynamic capabilities within Bergenborgshem. Moreover, to further prove and expand upon the adapted dynamic capabilities framework, research comparing the Bergenborgshem case study with another case in the same industry would be beneficial. Finally, applying the adapted dynamic capabilities framework to other industries would also further develop and potentially prove the relevance of the framework generated in this thesis.

7.1.2. Implications and Future Recommendations for Practitioners

While dynamic capabilities literature acknowledges the place that leaders hold in the organization, leaders within organizations may not connect their actions to organizational dynamic capabilities. Opportunities for maximizing organizational potential may be necessarily limited as a result. Additionally, dynamic capabilities terminology may be too vague and therefore inaccessible to lower and middle level organizational leaders. Thus, leaders and managers may benefit from the adapted framework developed in this thesis as it employs more accessible terminology and provides clear links between environment, leaders as actors, value creation and organizational core capabilities. A practitioner-friendly diagram providing a road map with user-friendly terminology could be beneficial to organizational managers who pursue innovation in the face of external environmental disruption, thereby enhancing organizational evolutionary fitness.

7.2. Summary

Increasingly, regions and municipalities must address their social sustainability challenges through social innovation aimed at solving identified problems and in line with the European Commission's (2021) recommendations as mentioned in the introduction of this thesis. The purpose of this thesis was to investigate an example of social innovation for positive change and to explore the leadership and dynamic capabilities of a social innovation housing company amid the COVID -19 pandemic challenges. Organizational dynamic capabilities were investigated through two perspectives: examining the processes through which the organization identifies, builds, and deploys capabilities and the leadership practices, competencies, and styles employed by the leaders relative to the capabilities. The aim and contribution of the thesis were multilayered to augment existing literature on the discourse of leadership as a core dynamic capability. To accomplish this, the thesis adapted a conceptual framework (Figure 3) based on the Heaton et al. (2020) previous framework (see Figure 2) and on Yin's (2017) recommendations. The adapted framework generated in this thesis offers the opportunity for future research in leadership, dynamic capabilities, and social innovation for social sustainability projects. Given the results of the study, the thesis purpose, aim and contribution has been achieved as described below.

To answer RQ1, the dynamic capabilities employed by all leadership levels had to be identified. Through an analysis of the data gathered through semi-structured interviews with a board member, the CEO, middle and lower management employees, as well as residents of Bergenborgshem's TLP, and external stakeholders, the following dynamic capabilities were identified: (1) Skilled and Appropriate Leaders; (2) Culture of Innovation; (3) Flexible Leadership Structure; and (4) Reliable, Transparent Communication. These four dynamic capabilities were identified as being essential to the Bergenborgshem leadership amid the COVID-19 global pandemic disruption.

When considering RQ2, the study results demonstrated that leaders interacted with the previously mentioned dynamic capabilities and that leaders supported team autonomy, engaged in customer and intra organization dialogue, and provided leadership support as shown in Figure 4. These leadership interactions led to the authors' discovery of Bergenborgshem's unique organizational dynamic capabilities. The strength of these capabilities was tested during the COVID-19 government-ordered health precautions which directly threatened the TLP project. The broader

dynamic capabilities interacting together and carried out by leadership supported the actions necessary for project leaders to deliver customer value to residents through the project disruption. Moreover, study results established that even under stressful conditions, leaders engaged in positive interactions and deployed useful transformations that increased customer value.

Figure 4: TLP leadership enhanced dynamic capabilities interactions in response to COVID-19 challenges

To conclude, this thesis presents a unique perspective on leadership and dynamic capabilities for social innovation projects employing an adapted framework that emphasizes the role of leaders. It is recommended that further research be conducted to better understand how leaders enhance and interact with dynamic capabilities for value creation for social innovation projects. Nevertheless, the study may help leaders to better understand how they can identify, build, and deploy their organizational dynamic capabilities in the face of disruption, even if the adapted framework may need further research for generalized application.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Interview guide for interviews with interviewee A and B (English version)

Background/warmup questions

- Consent Question: Do you consent to being recorded and that this data will be used in our thesis work?
- What did you do before becoming a leader at TLP?
- What is your title and role in the TLP project?
- Warm up question: What is the TLP? social innovation challenge?
 - What inspired you to tackle this challenge?

Leadership Questions

- In your role at TLP what is your approach to leadership?
- Has your approach changed from the beginning phase of the project through implementation (launch) to now?
 - If yes, how? If not, why do you think it has not?
- How do your colleagues approach leadership? In your opinion, what are their strengths and weaknesses?
- What is a recent example of a leadership challenge you faced?
- What values are most important to you as a leader and how do you apply them at TLP?
- How does politics influence the leadership process?

Dynamic Capability: Sensing and Shaping Opportunities

Finding opportunities, Individual capacity and Driving force:

- How are you defining new opportunities?
- How are you focusing on your residents' needs now?
- What is your driving force in your role at TLP?
- How do you perceive the surrounding business environment in Bergenborg?
- What would you say your advantages and disadvantages are as an innovative housing project?
- Can you describe a decision you had to make with incomplete information?
- How did you anticipate the need for the new mission- what, if anything, does this challenge in your opinion?
- What was the most significant change you brought about in TLP? What inspired you to take action?

Dynamic Capability: Seizing Opportunities

Enterprise structure, Procedures, Designs and Initiatives

- What is your role in achieving TLP's mission and vision?
- How do TLP residents and staff assist with achieving the mission and vision? Can you give an example of this in action?
- What briefly is your business model?
- How are you developing your ideas into reality?

- How do you select the ideas you are willing to invest in?
- How is the information flow within TLP?
- Would you describe TLP as rather more centralized or decentralized?
- How does TLP capture value within the organization?

**Dynamic Capability: Managing Threats/Reconfiguring
Changes, Barriers, Management Style**

- Can you describe a recent instance in which you learned something new about TLP?
- Can you give us an example of a leadership failure along the way to your current success? When did you realize it was a failure? What did you learn from it?
- How do you adapt to the surrounding business and social/economic/environment?
- How is running TLP different today than it was in the beginning?
- What if any external/partnership support do you receive?
- What are the greatest barriers you face as a business?

Appendix B: Interview guide for interviews with interviewee C, D, and G.

Leadership for Dynamic Capabilities: Strategic Leadership Disciplines

- In your role at TLP, what is your approach to leadership?
- Has your approach changed from the beginning phase of the project through implementation (launch) to now?
 - If yes, how? If not, why do you think it has not?
- What is a recent example of a leadership challenge you faced?
- What values are most important to you as a leader and how do you apply them at TLP?
- How does politics influence the leadership process?
- Who do residents go to at TLP if they have a problem or a new idea for the project?
- Is there a “leader” among the residents?
- Is there a particular style of leading and communicating at TLP? If yes, how would you describe it?
- If residents want to change something about TLP, how do they do this?

Dynamic Capability: Sensing and Shaping Opportunities

Finding opportunities, Individual capacity and Driving force:

- Do you see any potential opportunities or improvements for TLP?
 - If so, how have these ideas been communicated to anyone in the project group at Bergenborgshem?
 - Have any of these ideas been implemented?
- How are you defining new opportunities?
- How are you focusing on your residents’ needs now?
- What is your driving force in your role at TLP?
- Can you describe a decision you had to make with incomplete information?
- What was the most significant change you brought about in TLP? What inspired you to take action?

Dynamic Capability: Seizing Opportunities

Enterprise structure, Procedures, Designs and Initiatives

- What are some of the things that residents say they like about living in TLP?
 - Have these things been communicated to Bergenborgshem? If so, how? If not, why not?
- Has anything gone wrong or have any challenging issues occurred while you have worked in TLP?
 - How did you communicate to others that this thing had gone wrong/issue occurred? To whom did you communicate this?
 - How did the leadership at TLP react and fix this issue?
- What is your role in achieving TLP’s mission and vision?
- How is the information flow within TLP?

Dynamic Capability: Managing Threats/Reconfiguring

Changes, Barriers, Management Style

- What do you think the future of TLP looks like?
- Have there been changes with leadership since you arrived? If yes, how were those changes for you and the residents?
- How did Covid affect leading and opening TLP? What have you learned about TLP as a result?
- Can you describe a recent instance in which you learned something new about TLP?
- Can you give us an example of a leadership issue along the way to your current success? When did you realize it was an issue? What did you learn from it?
- How is running TLP different today than it was in the beginning?

- What are the greatest barriers TLP faces?

Other interesting questions:

- How is technology used at TLP? Can you describe it?
- Is there an interest among residents for any technology?

Appendix C: Follow up questions for interviewee C

Leadership

- Did you go through any leadership training through Bergenborgshem or any other employee development programs?
 - If so, what were your main takeaways?
- Even though you come to the project with 'fresh eyes' do you experience and /or observe a "Bergenborgshem way of leadership through your interactions with other employees in the organization?
 - If so could you describe your impressions and observations?
- In the interview you describe some of your approach to leadership as experimental. You mention you feel empowered by Bergenborgshem to "try new things". Do we understand correctly that your leadership is "situational"? So the situation, the circumstances, are a major part of how you decide to lead in one way or another?
 - If so, would you describe your leadership style as consistent but also flexible depending on the situation?

COVID-19 Disruption

- Covid has been a major disruption to the original plans for carrying out the social program at TLP. However much of the interview we learned that what you deal with is basic human community negotiation- making group decisions on behalf of everyone.
- Do you think then, that COVID-19 really has not had much of an impact on the governance issues at TLP? Even if people were meeting in person all the time- would the issues and challenges that come up in the community more or less be similar? You mentioned that the online school has been a significant hardship for the young immigrant residents.
- Are there any other ways that this COVID disruption- online school- affects the whole of TLP? It takes your time and skill to work with the residents who are struggling, but does it have an effect on the other residents or the way that the community is run? We did not get the impression that COVID was a terrible struggle for you- more that you experienced it as a challenge to be dealt with in just the same way as you deal with the resident issues.
- Is this a fair assessment? How would you like us to understand what the COVID disruption has been like from your job vantage point? Please use any words to describe it.

Appendix D: Interview guide for interview with Interviewees E and F (English version)

Leadership for Dynamic Capabilities: Strategic Leadership Disciplines

- Who do you go to at TLP if you have a problem or a new idea for the project?
- Is there a “leader” among the residents you live with?
- Is there a particular way that people “lead” at TLP? If yes, how would you describe it?
- If residents want to change something about TLP, how do they do this?

Dynamic Capability: Sensing and Shaping Opportunities

Finding opportunities, Individual capacity and Driving force:

- Do you see any potential opportunities or improvements for TLP?
 - Have these ideas been communicated to anyone in the project group at Bergenborgshem?
 - Have any of these ideas been implemented?

Dynamic Capability: Seizing Opportunities

Enterprise structure, Procedures, Designs and Initiatives

- What are some of the things that you like about living in TLP?
 - Have these things been communicated to Bergenborgshem? If so, how? If not, why not?
- Has anything gone wrong/issues occurred while you have lived in TLP?
 - How did you communicate that this thing had gone wrong/issue occurred? Who did you communicate this to?
 - How did the leadership at TLP react and fix this issue?

Dynamic Capability: Managing Threats/Reconfiguring

Changes, Barriers, Management Style

- What do you think the future of TLP looks like?
- Have there been changes with leadership since you arrived? If yes, how were those changes for you and the residents?
- What have you learned about TLP since you moved in?

Other interesting questions:

- How is technology used at TLP? Can you describe it?

Appendix E: Follow up questions for interviewees E and F

COVID DISRUPTION

You mentioned that because of covid you have not really gotten to experience the full power of the TLP project where you can interact quite a bit in shared spaces.

- Would you say that through the technological tools like TEAMS and Facebook that you have adjusted as a group to still get to know each other fairly well?
- You mention playing games together. Is that in person or over TEAMS like your house meetings?
- We did not get the impression that you are terribly upset by the COVID restrictions on physical /social distancing.
- Were you very upset in the beginning? If you were not upset by the restrictions, were other residents upset by this?
- Since residents like you agreed to live at TLP thinking you would have lots of interaction, have you still gotten together for social activities or cooking or eating together at TLP but just keeping your 2 meters distance?
- When you mentioned the gardening project for example, do people feel comfortable being together outside now either keeping a safe distance, or with masks or being vaccinated?

It sounds like most people in the house feel ok with using TEAMS and Facebook.

- Is this a fair interpretation or are you two more unusual in being comfortable?
- We got the impression that despite the significant setback that COVID has caused for the TLP social project that you still feel there has been strong benefits to the residents just by living there in a community.
- 7) Does just living in the house together even with social/physical restrictions solve the "involuntary loneliness" problem sufficiently?

Appendix F: Interview guide for interviews with interviewees H

- What is your knowledge of Bergenborgshem as an organization and the role it plays in Bergenborg?
- What is your awareness of Bergenborgshem's innovation history, leadership and capacity?
- What is your knowledge of Bergenborgshem leadership, management and projects in the years between 2015 and 2021?
- How would you characterize the leadership at Bergenborgshem in the following categories: Board level, Top Management (CEO) level, Mid-level Management
- What is your knowledge of the TLPhousing project- in particular, how would you describe the consumer value creation during the CoronaVirus Pandemic time period?
- If you are aware, how has TLP carried on through the CoronaVirus time period vis a vis leadership, delivering their stated value proposition while adhering to health and safety restrictions?

Appendix G: Interview guide for interviews with interviewees I

- What about TLP has inspired you to pursue a similar project?
- Would your housing project have an on-site Host as the TLP project does? What would their role be?
- In your opinion, is your housing company similar to Bergenborgshem ? In what ways?
- Do you see any opportunities for improving the TLP project model?
- Is there a particular style of leading and communicating at TLP? If yes, how would you describe it?
- What is your understanding of how TLP residents communicate with Bergenborgshem?
- TLP residents feel they “self-govern” through monthly and bi-weekly meetings. Is this your opinion after visiting? Is this the model you would also pursue in your project?
- Is it your understanding that TLP residents can make suggestions for changes and innovations in their residence? With whom do they communicate to the best of your knowledge to suggest or initiate change?
- How well does Helsingborgshem perform in your opinion on delivering their “value proposition” to the TLP residents?
- Are you aware of ways that Bergenborgshem have adjusted /responded to COVID-19 challenges at TLP?
- Given the challenges COVID has presented for TLP which is based on the residents spending time together, have you considered how you would cope with physical/social distancing issues in the future?
- With whom in Bergenborgshem do residents most interact, in your opinion?
- What are the greatest barriers TLP faces?
- What do you think the future of TLP looks like?

Appendix H: Informational letter sent to all interviewees (In Swedish, English version provided if requested)

Välkommen till intervju!

Vad är det för studie?

Vi, Megan Penhoet och Kathrine Widerberg Andersen, går programmet Ledarskap för Hållbarhet vid Malmö universitet. För vårt examensarbete gör vi en studie som undersöker hur den sociala innovationen TLP ledarskapsförmågor påverkas av att gå in i växt stadiet av "The Social Innovations Process model". Titeln på detta projekt är "Leadership and Dynamic Capabilities in the Growth Stage of a Social Innovation- An examination of The Loneliness Project in Bergenborg". Syftet är att undersöka och utforska hur ledarskapsförmågor inom TLP projektet i Bergenborg påverkas av att organisationen går in i tillväxtfasen av den sociala innovationsprocessen. För denna undersökning och utforskning kommer Dynamic Capabilities att användas för att förstå företagare inom social innovation, särskilt deras ledarskapsförmåga.

Hur går studien till?

Allt data kommer samlas via intervjuer som utförs genom Zoom eller Teams. Alla intervjuer kommer att spelas in för att hjälpa till med transkribering. Intervjuerna kommer utföras på svenska eller engelska. Om intervjuerna utförs på svenska kommer de för att transkriberas och sedan översättas till engelska. Ifall författarna av detta examensarbete behöver förtydligande eller har följdfrågor, kommer den intervjuade att kontaktas via e-post. Det är frivilligt att välja om man vill svara på denna e-post.

Deltagandet är frivilligt

Det är helt frivilligt att delta och du kan när som helst återkalla ditt samtycke utan att ange orsak. Alla svar och resultat som kommer oss till del behandlas på ett sådant sätt att inga obehöriga kan ta del av dem.

Vad händer med dina uppgifter?

Resultaten från denna studie kommer att utgöra del av ett examensarbete samt att de kommer att publiceras som artiklar i vetenskapliga tidskrifter och vid vetenskapliga konferenser. Personuppgifterna som samlas kommer att raderas efter forskningsprojektet har avslutats.

Ansvariga för studien

Huvudansvarig studenter för projektet är Megan Penhoet och Kathrine Widerberg Andersen, studenter på programmet Ledarskap för Hållbarhet vid Malmö universitet.

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